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Early-Exit SNNs On Neuromorphic Hardware

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Chapter 1

Introduction

This section covers the motivation behind the work, highlighting the relevance of the topic in the context of computer science, as well as the task, goal and intended results of the bachelor thesis.

1.1 Motivation

The history of Artificial Neural Networks (ANNs) is marked by challenges regarding the available computational resources.

While the earliest ANNs, like the Perceptron from F. Rosenblatt, worked with 500 to 1000 neurons in its hidden layer depending on the version [70], in today's ANNs parameter sizes in the realm of millions are not uncommon, like in the original BERT model from 2019 which used 110 million parameters in its Base version [19]. With the rise of Large Language Models, parameter spaces in the billions can be encountered in the GPT family [13].

The increased size and complexity comes with advances in computing power. While the Perceptron was only able to perform a classification of different simple objects [70], today's ANNs are able to create images, simulate conversations, are used in autonomous driving and even able to outperform humans in e.g. the game Go [45; 83; 85].

However, the technological advancements also come with a high cost. Especially with the boom of using Artificial Intelligence in the general population, most notably in the form of ChatGPT [65], and the worsening situation in terms of climate change [87], the resources needed to train and use Neural Networks (NNs) cannot be ignored.

The aim of reducing the resource usage of ANNs can be achieved by developing more efficient models, better training algorithms, inference models and more efficient hardware. An alternative to ANNs, founding on a strong inspiration from biology, also presents itself as a promising direction: Spiking Neural Networks (SNNs). They communicate through discrete events, only communicating when it is needed to transport information [56], in contrast to ANNs, which - in their general form - continuously forward information

through the network.

Another significant characteristic of SNNs is their biological realism. They closely resemble the way the neurons in the brain communicate and can be trained through biologically plausible learning algorithms, enabling the scientific field of computational neuroscience to implement models of (parts of) the brain in the form of NNs. [56; 57]

SNNs cover the software side. However, their distinct way of communication needs proper hardware support to support maximal efficiency. While the usage of standard hardware is possible, maximal efficiency gains are only possible through Neuromorphic Hardware (NH), which natively supports the spiking behaviour of SNNs by e.g. using specialised communication protocols and keeping the neuron's memory local to it. One such hardware is BrainScaleS. It is a partly-analog system developed at the University of Heidelberg and available through the open research infrastructure EBRAINS [21], Europe's digital infrastructure for brain research [20]. NH is the perfect match for SNNs. Also being inspired by the biological processes and structure in the brain, they provide native support for the sparse event-based communication used by SNNs. [12]

Taking a closer look at the training on SNNs, the already efficient signalling through spikes still presents options for improvement.

One strategy, also employed in ANNs, is to perform an early-exit, so stopping the model inference as soon as the model is confident enough in its prediction. Especially when aggregating the number of spikes over a time interval to determine the model's prediction, this can lead to less time - and therefore resources - needed [14]. Additionally, this form of faster or slower decisions based on confidence and urgency can be compared to the speed-accuracy-tradeoff (SAT) encountered in biology [11], again highlighting the possibility to learn from the brain to infer efficient computing paradigms.

1.2 Research Questions

This goal of this work is to combine the early-exit strategies applied to SNNs with NH - specifically BrainScaleS - in order to explore whether the increased inference speed and reduced spiking achieved in simulators on GPUs can be translated to NH. Therefore, a SNN using early-exit strategies will be trained on the NH.

Early-exit in simulators can be done quite easily by checking the model's confidence in intervals, stopping the simulation when the model is confident enough and continuing otherwise. BrainScaleS is a NH, notably even partly analog [68]. While software interfaces exist to run models on the hardware for a defined time [77], there is no possibility to stop these runs early, yet. Also the "stop-and-maybe-continue" possible in simulators faces the challenge of continuously evolving analog circuits in BrainScaleS.

Several research questions will be explored.

1. Will an early exit mechanism lead to reduced power usage of the system and can accuracy be kept high compared to non-early-exit models?
2. How can early-exit be implemented on the partly analog system, which challenges will occur due to its intricacies?

Chapter 2

Preliminaries

This section introduces the basic information for the three scientific areas combined in the topic covered in this thesis: neuroscience, neuromorphic hardware and machine learning with focus on SNNs.

It introduces signal processing in the brain, presenting the ideas which serve as inspiration for SNNs and NH, the basics of NH, SNNs and early-exit strategies.

2.1 Biological Background

The two main structures in the brain are neurons and synapses, shown in Fig. 1. Synapses connect the neurons which allows them to communicate through spikes. Spikes can arrive at the neuron's dendrites, the axon connects neurons across distances.

A spike is sent when the neuron's potential, increased by accumulating the signal from incoming spikes, reaches the neuron's spiking threshold. If no spikes arrive, the neurons potential trends towards a resting point. [43, Chapter 1.1-1.2] So spikes are only sent for and caused by information which needs to be communicated.

The communication happens via neurotransmitters, e.g. glutamate and GABA. On spiking, those neurotransmitters are released from the presynaptic neuron and transported to the postsynaptic neuron across the synapse. Arriving at the postsynaptic neuron, this affects the movement of ions into and out of the neuron, causing a change in its potential. [43, Chapter 3.1; 49]

This change can be an increase or decrease, which depends on the type of synapse, differing in the neurotransmitter released by the presynaptic neuron. An inhibitory synapse communicates through GABA and causes a decrease of the membrane potential of the postsynaptic neuron. An excitatory synapse utilises glutamate and increases the membrane potential of the postsynaptic neuron, pushing it closer to its spiking threshold. [43, Chapter 3.1; 49]

Figure 1: Basic structure of a neuron and synapse, image adapted from [73]

2.1.1 Neuron Models

The biological processes in the neurons are described by various mathematical models, varying in complexity and accuracy with which the biological processes can be reflected. For this thesis, two models are important: The Leaky Integrate-and-Fire (LIF) model, which is commonly used when implementing SNNs [14; 54; 55; 88; 89], and the more complex Adaptive Exponential Integrate-And-Fire (AdEx) model which BrainScaleS implements [68].

The LIF model is defined by two core equations. The first equation (1) describes the change in the membrane potential V over time, depending on the membrane time constant τ_m of the neuron and the input I from presynaptic neurons which is scaled by the resistance R of the neuron's membrane. Without input I , the neuron trends towards its resting potential V_{rest} . The second equation (2) models the reset of the neuron's potential to its reset potential V_{reset} after spiking at t_{spike} . [43, Chapter 1.3]

$$\tau_m \frac{dV}{dt} = -[V(t) - V_{rest}] + RI(t) \quad (1)$$

$$\text{At spike time: } \lim_{\delta \rightarrow 0; \delta > 0} V(t_{spike} + \delta) = V_{reset} \quad (2)$$

The AdEx model adds adaptation and an exponential to the spiking term.

Adaptation describes the process that a neuron either trends towards more or less frequent spiking shortly after it already spiked. One cause for it are the different time-dynamics of the ion gates in the membrane, which influences the speed with which the neuron's potential changes. [43, Chapter 6.3]

Fig. 2 shows how the membrane potential of a neuron changes when input spikes arrive, how it resets after spiking when reaching v_{thresh} and how it trends towards the resting potential v_{rest} in the absence of input spikes. These two behaviours are shared between the LIF and AdEx models. The effect of adaptation is visualised in the bottom right graph.

Figure 2: Evolution of membrane potential based on input spikes, leak and adaptation.

The AdEx model as used by BrainScaleS consists of four equations. The first equation (3) describes the change of the neurons potential V , evolving with the capacitance C of its membrane. The change depends on the potential's distance to the resting potential V_{rest} , multiplied by the leak conductance g_L which describes how fast ions can pass through the membrane. Additionally, the exponentially scaled distance to the spiking threshold V_{thresh} , the adaptation w and the current I from incoming spikes affect the neuron's potential over time. Δ_T controls the slope of the exponential, which models the steep increase in the neuron's potential as soon as the spiking threshold is reached.

Equation (4) and (6) describe the change of the adaptation. It changes in two ways, first it depends on the distance to the resting potential scaled by parameter a and the current adaptation. Second, a spike of the neuron adds the value b to the adaptation, modelling spike-triggered adaptation.

As before, the neuron's potential is reset to its reset potential V_{reset} on spike, described by equation (5). [68]

$$C \frac{dV}{dt} = -g_L[V(t) - V_{rest}] + g_L \Delta_T \exp\left(\frac{V(t) - V_{thresh}}{\Delta_T}\right) - w + I \quad (3)$$

$$\tau_w \frac{dw}{dt} = a[V(t) - V_{rest}] - w \quad (4)$$

$$\text{At spike time:} \quad V \rightarrow V_{reset} \quad (5)$$

$$w \rightarrow w + b \quad (6)$$

2.2 Spiking Neural Networks

This section provides a basic introduction to SNNs, a form of NNs based on the structures and observations in biology. The fundamentals needed for this thesis are presented and an introduction to the challenges encountered when training SNNs is given.

2.2.1 Differences To ANNs

In their basic structure, SNNs and ANNs are very similar. Both are made of neurons which are connected through weighted edges, resembling the synapses in biology. The neurons are placed in layers, commonly forming one input and output layer with a varying number of hidden layers in between. In both network types, the neurons output some kind of activation, based on their input signals. The strength of the activation can be controlled through parameters of the neuron, e.g. the bias in ANNs or the spiking threshold in SNNs. Fig. 3 shows this structure of a neural network, w being the weight of the directed connection, b the bias of the neuron. Incoming signals are aggregated, symbolised by the sum at the neurons. [40; 71]

Figure 3: Overview of neural network structure, based on [3]

However, this is where the differences begin. In ANNs, the activations are real numbers, calculated by applying e.g. the ReLU or sigmoid function to the weighted sum of inputs, leading to high-precision activations [40], which means that even a barely activated neuron outputs a signal to the neurons in the following layers. This causes a high computational cost, as also little activations cause computation in later layers, even if their impact on the model's output is negligible.

In SNNs, a neuron's activation is binary and only emitted if the neuron's activation, so membrane potential, reaches its spiking threshold. This causes the signals in SNNs to be much sparser than in ANNs, reducing the amount of computation which needs to happen. This sparseness of signals puts a higher emphasis on each single spike. [40; 56]

The second, even more significant difference to ANNs is that information in SNNs is carried by time [40]. Neurons used in SNNs are often LIF neurons [14; 54; 55; 88; 89], which means that continuous processes which influence the membrane potential exist. It is therefore crucial when a spike arrives at a neuron, as a few milliseconds can make the difference between causing a spike or not. Accordingly, the number of spikes per time also plays a huge role. The higher the amount, the quicker the postsynaptic neuron reaches its threshold, even if it quickly trends towards its leak potential.

2.2.2 Codes

As discussed, the timing of signals in an SNN is of high importance. We therefore must interpret the timing of the output spikes of the network to decode the networks output, as well as encode the input into the model in a way which conveys information through time. Eshraghian et al. provide a summary of commonly applied codes to solve these two challenges, shown in Fig. 4. The two types of codes look at the rate, so how many spikes per time, and the latency, so how soon spikes arrive. [40]

Figure 4: Overview of codes for spiking neural networks, based on [40]

Rate Codes

In rate codes, a higher number of spikes encodes a higher activation. Using rate codes for the output of the network reduces the risk that a neuron does not spike at all. This approach is also more error-tolerant, as single spikes carry less information than in latency codes, an error or delay in its transportation is therefore less severe.

However, rate codes also lead to a high energy usage, as the amount of needed communication and computation directly depends on the number of spikes. Additionally, the rate of spikes at the output neurons needs to be observed over a specific time-interval, leading to a higher inference latency. [40]

In biology, rate coding can be observed in neurons responding to movement in a particular direction in their receptive fields, as measured in the monkey brain [59].

Latency Codes

Latency codes work with less spikes and are therefore more energy efficient than rate codes. They encode information in the exact timing of spikes, an earlier spike encodes a higher activation. Next to reducing the energy usage, this also reduces the latency of the inference, as the output of the model can be determined as soon as the first output neuron spikes. This efficiency makes latency codes also biologically plausible, because the brain runs on very little energy.

While providing benefits, training with latency codes also presents challenges. The risk of quiet neurons is much higher, as the training happens with a smaller number of spikes. Also, the margin for error is slimmer, as each single spikes carries a lot of information. [40]

2.2.3 Cross Entropy Loss

Loss functions are used to calculate the error of the network. Training the model aims to reduce the loss by adjusting the learnable parameters, e.g. weights and neuron parameters, based on their contribution to the total loss. [40] Cross-Entropy is a commonly used loss function for SNNs [14; 54; 55; 89].

The following two equations are used to calculate the Cross-Entropy (CE) loss L_{CE} . First, the probability p_i for each of the N_C output classes is calculated using the activation c_i of the neuron as input to the softmax function. The use of the exponential emphasises high values, resulting in a larger distance to smaller values compared to the calculation without it. The target vector y_i is one-hot encoded, targeting exactly one output neuron as the correct one. The loss L_{CE} is the sum of normalised probabilities multiplied with their value of the target vector y_i . [40; 86]

Therefore, the CE loss is smallest if the probability for the correct output is largest, so close to one, resulting in a sum close to zero from the logarithm.

$$p_i = \frac{e^{c_i}}{\sum_{i=1}^{N_C} e^{c_i}} \quad L_{ce} = - \sum_{i=1}^{N_C} y_i \log(p_i)$$

Using rate codes, the neuron's activation c_i corresponds to its spike count. Latency codes require an additional translation, because lower times, so earlier spikes, signal higher activation. Simple solutions to map the lower spike times s_i to higher values for c_i are to calculate the inverse $c_i = 1/s_i$ or reverse $c_i = -s_i$. [40]

2.2.4 Challenges During Training

SNNs' unique property of information encoded in time also presents unique challenges. To train a model based on labelled data, the error must be determined, e.g. with the described CE loss, and then used to calculate its gradient with respect to the different learnable parameters like the weights of the connections. This gradient is used to determine the necessary adjustment to the parameters. [40]

The issue with spikes is, that they are not differentiable. A function plotting the spike count of a single neuron jumps from 0 to 1 and back in an instant, leaving no usable gradient.

Multiple solutions for this issue exist. Instead of using the existence of spikes as signal, one can work with the spike times. Time is continuous, so the gradient of the spike time can be calculated as long as the neuron spikes once. Alternatively, surrogate gradients can be used. They replace the non-differentiable spikes with a differentiable function, e.g. depending on the membrane potential. [40; 56]

Next to the challenges in credit assignment, calculating the error of the network can also be challenging. Depending on the training approach and target value, a neuron must spike to be able to calculate and propagate its error, whether through surrogate gradients,

the spike time or the spike count. It therefore needs to be ensured that the neurons do not become silent which would cause the model to not learn anymore. [40]

The desired biological plausibility is another source for challenges. Backpropagation is commonly applied to ANNs and uses the chain rule of differentiation to propagate the error through the hidden layers of the network [81]. But its version for SNNs, backpropagation through time, is biologically implausible because it depends on information about past membrane potentials and spikes from all other neurons. The brain is considered to work locally and temporally sparse, so without such a memory of past spikes, especially across all neurons, which conflicts with this approach for credit assignment. Biologically more plausible is E-Prop, which can even include the adaptation of the AdEx model and only depends on local information to calculate the gradients, fitting better to the sparsity in the brain. [7; 40]

2.3 Neuromorphic Hardware

SNNs communicate via spikes and use continuously evolving neurons as nodes in their layers. Standard hardware does not provide optimal support for both. Neuromorphic, so brain-inspired, hardware is based on the same biological mechanisms as SNNs. Hence, such systems provide more native support for spike-based communication and the continuous behaviour of neurons.

Surveying the state of the art in 2019, Bouvier et al. define the two purposes of neuromorphic hardware as: "leverage neuroscience discoveries to realise low-power machine learning or to improve performances" and to "implement on-chip bio-plausible dynamical elements" [12].

They note that one difficulty when simulating SNNs comes from the common need to discretise time, so sequentially calculate the neuron's state in timesteps. High accuracy calls for a short timestep, which on the other hand increases the computational cost and time needed for computation. Also, necessary memory accesses present a bottleneck, which leads them to the goal of distributing and parallelising storage and computation. [12]

This section provides a brief overview about different NH and their solutions to these challenges.

Major types of NH are digital and analog systems. Analog systems can implement a detailed model of neurons through the use of specialised circuitry, while digital systems update the neuron's state in discrete time-intervals. A high-level comparison of different design approaches can be found in [12], while [42] compares large-scale NH systems.

BrainScaleS is the focal system of this thesis. It is an analog system, solving the memory bottleneck issue by storing neuron parameters, synapse configurations and weights in SRAM local to the neurons and synapses. This prevents the need to access shared memory. Information about e.g. the membrane potential does not need to be stored explicitly, as the analog computation circuitry of the neuron contains this information in form of a voltage in a capacitor. This voltage is continuously updated based on incoming voltage and current, configured through tuneable conductances, having no need for discretised timesteps to calculate the updates. [68]

Another partly analog system is Neurogrid. Similarly to BrainScaleS, it implements neurons and synapses in analog circuits. However, in contrast to BrainScaleS which uses a dedicated synapse per connection of two neurons, they use shared synapses and dendrites. Each neuron is connected to four shared synapses and receives the spike-information targeted to its address. This approach effectively reduces the communication if neighbouring neurons share the same spikes. The routing is implemented by a tree-like organisation of cores, each containing its own SRAM that can be used to configure the routing of spike packets. It outscals BrainScaleS, being able to simulate a network with a million neurons and billions of synapses across multiple cores. [8]

The digital system TrueNorth has a similar scale as Neurogrid. It combines 4096 cores on each chip, each core containing 256 neurons and 64k synapses, so supporting over a million neurons. Memory distribution is achieved by locating storage for synapse connections, neuron parameters and their membrane potential on each core. The membrane potential must be calculated explicitly, which highlights the disadvantage compared to analog hardware. TrueNorth makes use of an asynchronous approach to reduce the computational cost. Using a local clock which only ticks when an incoming spike signal arrives for the neurons in the core, the neurons only perform computations when necessary. [4]

The extension of TrueNorth, NorthPole, a digital system presented 8 years later in 2023, also follows the approach to centralise memory per core. However, through eliminating redundancies present in TrueNorth, NorthPole effectively has over 600 times the memory available for parameter storage. In performance-critical sections, the memory is even intertwined with the computation, proving an even stronger locality than its predecessor. Allowing the choice between 2-, 4- and 8-bit precision, the tradeoff between accuracy and computational throughput can be chosen based on the application. However, the system only supports inference, which means that the training of a SNN needs to happen on another system. [58, Supplementary Materials; 58; 60]

Surpassing the scale of TrueNorth, the digital system SpiNNaker can be scaled to a system of over 65k chips with 18 cores per chip, providing billions of neurons and trillions of synapses. It uses globally asynchronous communication to reduce power consumption and enable high interconnectivity between neurons. Similar to the other systems, it uses memory local to each core and running at core speed for frequently used data. For synaptic information, a larger block of memory is shared between cores in a chip, as this information is only needed when a spike arrives. [67] Version 2 of the system switches from 130nm to 22nm technology, increasing the number of cores to 152 per chip. 35k SpiNNaker2 chips are combined into a system with 5 million cores, the largest brain-like supercomputer in the world. [44; 48]

Summarised, all NH share the same challenges: Neurons and synapses need storage which can be accessed quickly and in parallel in order to support fast, distributed computation across the SNN. Spike information needs to be routed between neurons without creating communication bottlenecks.

A common theme across the presented digital systems is the use of different layers of memory, providing high locality for commonly used information. Additionally, synchronous operation is combined with asynchronous approaches, like the event-based routing in

SpiNNaker or the local, asynchronously controlled clocks in TrueNorth.

Different technical solutions to increase the computational efficiency had to be found, like the tree-based routing in Neurogrid or the choice between different precisions in NorthPole to allow the user a choice between cost and accuracy.

The scale of the systems varies greatly, the presented digital systems leading in terms of scale. BrainScaleS is the smallest one by far, due to the current limitation to a single chip. Work towards a larger scale system was mentioned in 2021 [47]. Currently, the development towards connecting multiple chips through Field-Programmable Gate Arrays (FPGAs) is in progress, software for this is already integrated in the libraries for the system. Later, a faster integration is planned, possibly by splitting the chip into chiplets and using chiplet interconnections to replace the slow FPGAs ¹. A unique feature of BrainScaleS is its acceleration, providing a thousand-fold acceleration compared to biological real-time [68].

Remarkably, the Perceptron mentioned in the introduction was implemented as the mark I Perceptron machine, a hardware to simulate different types of perceptrons. It contained components which "switch on and transmit excitation onward to the next layer only when the sum of their input excitation exceeds a certain threshold". The components were connected in three layers: input, association and output. [46] Showing a clear similarity to spiking neurons connected through synapses, it could be called an early form of NH, developed in 1958.

2.4 Early-Exit

This section provides a biological motivation for early-exit, as well as highlighting the general idea in SNNs and ANNs. A more detailed discussion of implementations follows in section 3.2.

2.4.1 Decision Making In The Brain

As mentioned, the early-exit strategies applied to SNNs in this work can be compared to the SAT in biology. It describes the phenomenon that when making decisions, decision makers have to make a tradeoff between the time they need to arrive at a response and the accuracy of that response [11].

Compared to the early-exit in SNNs, the goal of stopping when the perceived accuracy of the decision is high enough is shared between the two.

In a review paper, Bogacz et al. summarise insights from various experiments investigating the SAT, often involving monkeys and humans. The experimental data suggests that a strong perceived urgency of the decision, so a focus on speed, increases the neural activity in brain-areas responsible for decision making which may correlate with an increased spiking activity of the neurons. [11; 64]

Also focusing on decision-making, however not on different urgencies but decisions with varying numbers of options, Churchland et al. performed experiments on monkeys. [15] They presented a set of moving dots to the monkeys which had to look into the direction

¹E. Müller, personal communication, Feb 12, 2026

in which the dots were moving. In the trials, the speed and direction of dot movement, as well as the number of choices - two or four - differed.

Measuring the firing rate in the lateral intraparietal area (LIP), a brain area responsible for eye movement and related decision-making [84], they find that the firing rates right before the decision were similar across two and four choice tasks. This suggests a fixed threshold for decisions. Looking at the buildup of the firing rate, they find that the rate of this buildup does neither depend on dot movement speed, direction nor the picked choice, but on the number of choices. For two choices, the rise of the firing rate is much stronger, which the authors interpret as a sign of cost for the time passing, the cost being higher for less options, reflecting an urgency to finish the decision-making process.

Those insights suggest that the brain has an internal perception of time passing while a decision is made and that the cost of the passed time - influenced by an additional external urgency or not - influences the neuronal activity and therefore the time taken to accumulate evidence for the decision. Plainly summarising, the subject's brains seem to act with the thought: I should not use much time for this simple decision.

2.4.2 Early Exit In NNs

The previous section presented examples how the brain speeds up decisions based on faced urgency or the complexity of a decision. The examples showed how a subject decides to stop gathering an input signal, i.e. stopping to observe the moving dots, making a decision based on the information gathered until now. [15] The early-stopping therefore does not only apply to the interpretation of the outputs or internal signals of the network, but also affects the input neurons.

The higher neural activity observed by Bogacz et al. [11] could suggest that the brain focuses on lower latency for the response while accepting a higher energy usage for the increased activity. However, energy in the body can be sparse and the brain takes around 20% of it. As Padamsey et al. summarise, existing studies show that development in various animals is slowed or impaired when faced with challenging cognitive tasks. Also, the brain reduces its energy spending on costly operations, e.g. long-term memory, when faced with resource scarcity. [66] This highlights that cognitive operations take up a lot of energy, while possibly even being prioritised over other processes in the body. Still, a lack of energy also negatively impacts the brain.

Sharing the goals of efficiently managing available energy and reducing latency, the early-exit applied to SNNs and ANNs shows clear parallels to the early-exit in biology. In general, we want to stop the inference as soon as the model is confident enough in the decision [55; 69; 89]. Approaches differ by the time and place where the exit happens, as well as the determination of confidence.

Early-exit in ANNs and SNNs mostly focuses on the output layer and the hidden layers. An approach for ANNs is to add branches which allow the model to exit from a hidden layer before the signal is forwarded to the next layer [69]. This can be especially effective in models with a high number of layers, as the amount of possible skipped computation also increases. The higher number of layers can then be used only for difficult inputs.

For SNNs, early-exit strategies use rate-codes and / or interpret the membrane potential at the output layer. Observing those variables over a flexible duration allows the collection of information to determine the point in time when the model is confident enough in its decision.

The next chapter will take a closer look at these early-exit strategies and present the state of the art for early-exit in SNNs. This includes approaches to determine the confidence as well as how to train models for the early-exit during inference.

Chapter 3

Current State Of The Art

Early-exit strategies for SNNs can be motivated twofold. First, they reduce the latency, making the model's prediction available earlier. Secondly, they can lead to a reduced energy usage by requiring shorter computation. This section explores alternatives to and variants of early-exit strategies and highlights how this work fits to existing research.

3.1 Spike Count Reduction

Generally speaking, reducing the number of spikes produced by an SNN leads to a lower power usage, as the spikes determine the number of packets to send, the voltage to accumulate in the neurons and possible further spikes caused by them. The reduction can be achieved by using latency-based coding techniques instead of rate codes. Latency codes reduce the spike count because the model is trained to time its output spike(s) to transmit information instead of using the amount of spikes for the strength of the signal. [40] Latency coding also reduces the inference time, because no output spikes need to be aggregated over time.

Using latency codes at the output layer, so making the decision based on the first arriving spike, is essentially early-exit without a confidence threshold. This can lead to worse accuracy, as even an output with low confidence causes the inference to stop.

Additionally, as described by [40], training SNNs becomes challenging when neurons do not spike, as the loss can only be calculated and propagated through the layers when communication happened between neurons. Rate codes generally lead to a higher spike count, reducing the risk for such dead neurons, while also making training easier by reducing the impact of small changes to single spikes.

Alternatively, instead of reducing the number of spikes per neuron, the number of connections can be limited. Billaudelle et al. describe an approach to synapse pruning with the motivation of working with limited resources of NH, only keeping the most impactful connections per neuron. [10] Overall, this again reduces the spike count, because less neurons transmit spikes between each other.

3.2 Early Exit In SNNs

The model’s confidence in its prediction must be measured in order to determine the correct time to end the inference without compromising accuracy. Approaches differ in the output signals which are used to calculate the confidence and the use of static or dynamic thresholds for the confidence.

SEENN-1, described by Li et al., examines the highest output of the model, comparing the softmax of the model’s outputs to a static confidence threshold. [55] Similarly to SEENN-1, Dynamic Confidence described by Li et al. also utilises the softmax of the model’s outputs and focuses on the highest value. They utilise a Pareto Front to determine a confidence threshold per timestep and pick a value based on the tradeoff between loss of accuracy and reduction of timesteps. [52]

The above approaches could be described as absolute confidence, focusing on only the maximum output of the model. In contrast, SNNCutoff compares the top-k outputs of the model and compares the distance between them. This relative confidence is based on the assumption that a higher difference signals a stronger confidence in the top prediction. [89]

Similarly to SNNCutoff, DT-SNN also utilises multiple outputs of the model. They calculate the entropy of the softmax of the model’s outputs and compare it to a threshold to determine the correct time for early-exit. To measure the effect, they compare their model’s impact on the energy-delay product on in-memory hardware and a GPU. [54]

Instead of the above static thresholding, SEENN-2 utilises a policy network which works on the input and corresponding output of the SNN and receives rewards based on the earliness of the picked timestep to stop the inference and the correctness of the SNN’s prediction. The policy network learns to use more time for more difficult input examples, which leads to an improved accuracy-latency tradeoff. [55]

All of the above approaches rely on the model’s confidence in its decision. Based on the observation that models tend to be overly confident in their prediction, SpikeCP utilises tools from conformal prediction, quantifying the model’s distance between confidence and accuracy. Their approach ensures that the model’s confidence stays below its accuracy. Similar to SEENN-1, it can be applied to any pre-trained SNN, but also used to train a model with awareness of the predicted set that early-exits based on the number of values it is highly confident in. What counts as high confidence is again defined through a static threshold, chosen per stopping time. [14] This set-based approach differs from the above, which train based on the confidence in single outputs.

3.3 Learning For Early Exit

While some early-exit strategies, e.g. SEENN-1 and SpikeCP, can be applied to any SNN, they are most effective for models which produce high confidence and high accuracy

predictions early. To achieve this, specialised training approaches were developed.

Deng et al. combine Temporal Efficient Training (TET)-loss and Time Inheritance Training (TIT). TET loss is calculated for every timestep and combines CE loss with Mean Squared Error (MSE) as regularisation to prevent negative impact on learning from noise occurring during every timestep. TIT proposes a two-step training. First, training the model on short simulation time, enforcing the goal of correct predictions as early as possible. Afterwards, the model is further trained, this time on a longer simulation time, focusing on increasing the accuracy. [17]

Following the same goal, Wu et al. add a regulariser of the cosine similarity to the CE loss during training with SSNCutoff, aiming to maximise the cosine similarity between the model's spike output (approximated by membrane potential) and the target spikes, training the model to not only produce good results at the last timestep. [89]

Similarly to the two approaches above, SpikeCP also adds a term to the CE loss. Their term is based on an approximation of the (non-differentiable) size of the set of high-confidence values the model returns. Adding it to the loss helps the model learn to aim for a smaller size early while keeping accuracy high, which is controlled via the CE. [14]

3.4 Early Exit In ANNs

The idea of early-exit can also be applied to ANNs. Instead of inspecting the output of the model over different timesteps, ANNs, especially Deep NNs, incorporate the early exit into earlier layers of the model, allowing to stop the inference before passing through the later layers.

This approach does not only lead to faster decisions and reduction of computational cost, but also can prevent that correct signals in early layers get lost by wrong interpretation in later ones, increasing the accuracy. [69]

The early-exit strategies face the same issues as SNNs: The model's confidence in the branches must be determined to check if an early-exit is valuable. Like in SNNs, this can happen via static thresholds e.g. on softmax or entropy, or through dynamic policies which take the model's input into account. [69]

Li et al. investigate the training of such models with intermediate classifiers. They find that transferring the knowledge between the classifiers, e.g. through dense connections between them, can improve the accuracy of the resulting model. [53]

The approach of early-exit through intermediate classifiers was also explored for deep SNNs. BlocTrain splits the model into multiple blocks, each consisting of a few layers and a classifier, which are trained after each other. Later blocks are trained on inputs which were difficult for the previous block, so classified with low accuracy. During inference, the blocks are applied after each other, allowing to stop the processing when the early classifiers are confident enough, e.g. determined by the softmax of the intermediate outputs. [76]

3.5 Potential Of This Work

Early-exit strategies present themselves as promising approach to combine the training qualities of rate codes with the latency and efficiency benefits of latency codes.

Combined with a suitable loss and learning algorithm, early-exit-SNNs can achieve competitive accuracy. [52; 55; 89]

All discussed approaches for early-exit were evaluated on standard GPUs. Therefore, the feasibility of these approaches on NH, as well as the impact on energy usage is an area lacking exploration. Li et al. make explicit, that "the real power saving when running on neuromorphic hardware is unknown to us" [52].

Even though they did not work with NH, Bhattacharjee et al. investigated the power usage of SNNs on specialised accelerators. They find that the spike count is one of the relevant factors for energy usage and achieve a significant power saving of nearly 50% when applying DT-SNN, so an early-exit strategy, to a VGG model. [9] This highlights that early-exit strategies can be also effective on analog hardware.

Multiple experiments were successfully performed with BrainScaleS in-the-loop or on-chip. Ranging from simple classification to reinforcement learning, [68] this proves the versatility of the system, making it a suitable system for the implementation in this work.

This work will investigate if and how early-exit strategies can be used on BrainScaleS and whether the efficiency gains measured on GPUs [52; 55] and the accelerators [9] can be replicated on this partly-analog neuromorphic hardware.

3.6 Why BrainScaleS

This thesis chose BrainScaleS as system for implementing the SNN. Being a partly analog hardware, this poses a series of additional challenges. So why was this hardware chosen for this thesis?

Early-exit is quite well evaluated on digital hardware, which is used by all approaches presented in the SotA. As mentioned by Li et al., an evaluation on NH is missing [52].

Using digital NH would stay closer to the existing research. Analog NH diverges more, behaving differently due to limitations of the hardware in size and function, as well as due to the continuous nature of the neurons modelled in the analog circuits.

The implementation on analog NH is therefore more challenging, which the author personally finds more intriguing. Additionally, further efficiency on the already very efficient analog hardware would provide a strong argument for the usefulness of early-exit.

Chapter 4

Early-Exit On BrainScaleS

The previous chapters provided an introduction to the relevant neuroscience, machine learning and hardware and introduced the state of the art regarding early-exit in SNNs. This chapter focuses on BrainScaleS and investigates which of the presented early-exit strategies are feasible on the hardware. First, the system and its software stack will be introduced shortly. Hardware restrictions relevant for the implementation will be highlighted, and the feasibility of the presented early-exit approaches will be discussed.

4.1 Hardware Implementation

As mentioned, BrainScaleS is a partly-analog system. A high-level overview of the chip is shown in Fig. 5 and 6. This thesis always refers to BrainScaleS version 2.

Figure 5: High-Level structure of a chip, taken from [68]

Figure 6: Detailed view of the top right quadrant of the chip, taken from [23]

The neurons and synapses are implemented in the analog core of the chip, marked by the dashed line in Fig. 6. The synapse array implements the connections from incoming spike signals via the synapse drivers on the left to the neurons at the bottom of the array. Each synapse in the array contains local storage for its sign, source address, the weight of the connection and a sensor for the correlation between incoming spikes and spikes of the connected postsynaptic neuron. This is useful for biologically plausible learning rules, e.g. Spike-Time Dependent Plasticity. A synapse is statically connected to its neuron at the bottom of the column. Fig. 6 also shows how the neuron’s parameters are stored directly next to the neuron circuits in the analog parameter storage. All parameters, so e.g. addresses, weights and thresholds, can be configured, a FPGA implements the connection between the chip and the host computer. [68]

The Column Analog-to-Digital Converter (CADC) above the synapse array provides access to the neuron states, e.g. the membrane potential, as well as the correlation measurements between the pre- and postsynaptic spikes per synapse. The CADCs are connected to two Plasticity Processing Units (PPUs), one at the top and one at the bottom of the chip as visible in Fig. 5. The PPU’s are digital and consist of multiple vector units as well as a general purpose processor, allowing to efficiently calculate parameter updates, calibrate the chip and simulate environments for model training on the chip. [68] The components of a PPU are shown in Fig. 7.

The connection on the chip is implemented through a digital event router. Spike events from the neuron are sent as voltage pulses which are serialised into a bit stream, together with the address of the neuron as source. Multiple lanes run in parallel to support a high communication throughput, each is responsible for routing the spikes of 64 neurons. The spike router is the big cross in Fig. 5. Each synapse driver located on the sides of the spike router is connected to one lane and two rows in the synapse matrix. It receives all spike events on that lane and mirrors it to both rows in the matrix. One row contains only inhibitory synapses, while the other one contains only excitatory synapses, positioned in an alternating manner across the matrix. [6; 41; 72] This mirroring logic enables BrainScaleS to also support negative weights. These connections are shown in Fig. 8.

This combination of analog components which can be accessed in parallel through the CADCs and the flexible digital PPU’s allows BrainScaleS to efficiently support even complex plasticity rules for the synapses, providing a high flexibility for the training of SNNs. [68]

Noteworthy about BrainScaleS is its 1000-fold acceleration compared to biological realtime. This is made possible by the analog implementation of the neurons and synapses. One example for this is the implementation of the exponential term in the AdEx model which makes use of the exponential subthreshold dynamics present in transistors [1].

Such circuit-level details about the implementation are described by Aamir et al. in [1; 2] where the interested reader can explore the circuitry further.

Figure 7: Components of the PPU, taken from [41]

Figure 8: Synapse matrix. Synapses listen to spikes with the same color. *Inh* marks inhibitory synapses and neuron connections, *Ex* marks excitatory ones. Based on [23]

4.2 Software To Access BrainScaleS

Software access to the hardware is supported at different layers of abstraction.

At the lowest layer, one can write programs for the PPU s using C++. The general purpose part of the PPU s , blue in Fig. 7, implements a subset of the embedded Power instruction set architecture which enables the use of the GNU compiler collection. Support for the vector units was added by the developing team of BrainScaleS. Using this software stack, one can write programs for the PPU s to access neurons and synapses by directly reading and writing register words. Single register access is abstracted away to ensure correct usage of the underlying protocols. Alternatively, the provided hardware abstraction layer can be used. It provides access to properly named and typed containers, e.g. `AtomicNeuron` with an `enable_leak` boolean or a `PlacedConnection` which identifies a synapse in the matrix. This software stack also supports running experiments, either completely on-chip or in interaction with the host computer. [24; 25; 61; 68]

Listing 1 shows an example using `grenade`, the library responsible for placing the network on the chip, and `lola`, the logical layer which defines containers that contain logical groups of registers.

```

1 PlacedConnection conn = PlacedConnection(); // connection from grenade
2 conn.synapse_row; // get row in synapse matrix
3 conn.synapse_on_row; // get column in synapse matrix
4
5 AtomicNeuron neuron = AtomicNeuron(); // neuron from lola
6 neuron.leak.v_leak = 123;
7 neuron.adaptation.enable = true;
8 neuron.threshold.v_threshold = 222;

```

Listing 1: Working with neurons and connections using BrainScaleS’ hal, based on [61]

Moving up a layer of abstraction, we can use the python library PyNN. It supports a hardware / simulator agnostic definition of networks built from neurons and synapses. The software works with the abstractions `Population` and `Projection`, which group neurons or synapses respectively, making the definition of large networks easier. The intent of PyNN is that each backend, e.g. hardware like BrainScaleS and SpiNNaker or simulators like NEST, provides their own implementation of the specific code for neurons and synapses which works with their backend. PyNN provides the higher level abstractions. [16] BrainScaleS provides their backend implementation in the python library `pynn-brainscales`, utilising their lower-level C++ libraries. It defines the class `HXNeuron` which provides access to all neuron parameters and can be used with PyNN's Projections. [77] Listing 2 shows how a `Population` of one AdEx neuron gets connected to a `Population` of ten LIF neurons using a `Projection`.

```

1 import pynn_brainscales.brainscales2 as sim
2
3 # create a neuron with enabled adaptation
4 adex_neuron = sim.Population(size=1, cellclass=sim.cells.HXNeuron(
5     adaptation_enable=True
6 ))
7 # create 10 LIF neurons with a custom reset voltage
8 lif_neurons = sim.Population(size=10, cellclass=sim.cells.HXNeuron(
9     reset_v_reset=-42))
10
11 sim.Projection(
12     # connect the neurons ...
13     adex_neuron, lif_neurons, connector=sim.AllToAllConnector(),
14     # ... using a weighted synapse
15     synapse_type=sim.synapses.StaticSynapse(weight=42)
16 )

```

Listing 2: Working with neurons and synapses using PyNN, based on [29]

In the highest layer of abstraction, BrainScaleS can be accessed through the python library `hxtorch`. It utilises the same C++ libraries as `pynn-brainscales` and works as a wrapper for the popular python library `PyTorch`, which is commonly used for defining and training ANNs. [5; 62; 75] Listing 3 scetches how both libraries can be used together, combining the model definition, loss function and utilities for backpropagation.

```

1 class SNN(torch.nn.Module):
2     def __init__(self, ...) -> None:
3         self.linear_output = Synapse(64, 10, ...) # num in, num out
4         self.neuron_output = hxsnn.LI(size=10, ...)
5
6     def forward(self, inputs: torch.Tensor) -> torch.Tensor:
7         # pass spikes as input, read output from neurons
8         g = self.linear_output(hxsnn.LIF0bservables(spikes=inputs))
9         y = self.neuron_output(g)
10        hxsnn.run(self.exp, inputs.shape[0])
11        # ...
12
13 class Model(torch.nn.Module):
14     def forward(self, inputs: torch.Tensor) -> torch.Tensor:
15         spikes = self.encoder(inputs)
16         traces = self.network(spikes) # self.network = the SNN above
17         return self.decoder(traces).clone()
18

```

```
19 def run_epoch(model: torch.nn.Module, loader: DataLoader, ...) -> Tuple:  
20     for data, target in loader:  
21         scores = model(data.to(dev)) # forward()  
22         loss = torch.nn.functional.nll_loss(scores, target.to(dev))  
23  
24         loss.backward() # backpropagation  
25         optimizer.step()
```

Listing 3: Working with a SNN using hxtorch and PyTorch, based on [30]

4.3 Working With The Hardware

This section explores considerations which need to be made when working with the hardware. This includes necessary translations between the hardware and software, as well as restrictions regarding the available information for training and the value ranges for parameters.

4.3.1 Misalignment Between Neurons

The neurons are implemented as analog circuits. This causes two kinds of misalignments, described by [22]. First, the recording of e.g. the membrane potentials does not happen at exactly the same time. Even when recording two neurons with the identical evolution of membrane potentials, this can cause small mismatches, because the analog circuits evolve continuously. We cannot press pause on the hardware in order to freeze the values. This also causes even neurons with the exact same configuration to spike at different times, because they do not receive the input spike events at exactly the same time. Secondly, it is not possible to create 512 100% equal circuits for the neurons due to semiconductor fabrication variations. This causes neurons with the same parameters (e.g. in PyNN) to have e.g. different thresholds, time constants and reset potentials.

This effect can be reduced through calibration. Each night, the behaviour of the neurons is recorded and a calibration is calculated which tweaks the parameters of each single neuron in a way that reduces the effect of these fixed pattern variations. [26] Fig. 9 shows how the measured membrane potential and spikes of two neurons changes across simulation runs. The differences are much larger without calibration.

Figure 9: Membrane potential (obs v) and spikes of two neurons, with (left) and without (right) calibration.

4.3.2 Parameter Resolution

The synapses and neurons have local SRAM for the parameters, the neuron’s membrane potential is stored in its analog circuit. This locality comes with limitations to the size of the storage, leading to the weights of the synapses being restricted to 6 bit and the neuron’s membrane potential to 8 bit. [80]

These restrictions must be considered when training SNNs, i.e. adjusting the weights. To align with the hardware, [30] uses a weight saturation function to restrict the weights from -63 up to 63. Such a function is also provided by the hxtorch library. [78]

4.3.3 Scaling The Membrane Potential

In addition to limiting the parameters to the allowed ranges, further scaling should be applied. As presented in [63], scaling the neuron’s membrane potential to 0 for V_{rest} to 1 for V_{th} simplifies the LIF equations.

On BrainScaleS, this serves the additional purpose of aligning the synapse weights and membrane potential measured in hardware (by the ADCs) with the software values. This is essential to be able to work with the same numeric scales, ensuring that learned changes to the parameters have the desired effect on the behaviour in hardware. This is particularly important for backpropagation and the needed gradient calculation. The forward pass is performed on the hardware, while the backward pass is calculated in software. If the parameters and measurements do not align between both, the model does not learn properly, because the calculated weight updates are not correct. [27]

The factors for the scaling can be obtained by measuring the baseline membrane potential of a few neurons without input spikes and the spiking threshold when sending many input spikes. The baseline and scaling factor can be passed to the neuron constructor provided by hxtorch. [27]

Fig. 10 shows how the scaling aligns the hardware measurements with the software values.

Figure 10: Effect of scaling on the alignment between the membrane potential measured in hardware (blue) and software (red). Left: no alignment, middle: hardware values shifted to start at 0, right: hardware values scaled to 0 - 1. Created with code from [27].

4.3.4 Value Recording

The neuron attributes which can be recorded depend on whether PyNN or hxtorch are used to define the SNN. Additionally, some information can only be recorded for a limited number of neurons.

Using PyNN, one can define which observables to record on the population, as shown in listing 4. In total, five observables are available: The spikes of the neuron and four analog observables, the membrane potential, the inputs from synapses and the value of the adaptation. However, restrictions apply. For a population of size one, only one of the analog observables can be recorded next to the spikes. For populations larger than size 2, none of the analog observables can be recorded. [32]

```

1 pop = pynn.Population(1, pynn.cells.HXNeuron(
2     leak_v_leak=750,
3     threshold_v_threshold=300,
4     reset_v_reset=260)
5
6 # available: ['spikes', 'v', 'exc_synin', 'inh_synin', 'adaptation']
7 observables = ['spikes', 'v']
8
9 pop.record(observables)

```

Listing 4: Recording neuron values with PyNN

hxtorch allows the recording of the neurons membrane potential, spikes and input current from the synapses. The membrane potential can be recorded via the CADC or the Membrane Analog-to-Digital Converter (MADC), the MADC provides a much higher resolution but can only record a single neuron.

Unlike PyNN, there is no restriction to the number of neurons for which to record the current and membrane potential via the CADCs. Listing 5 shows how the recording can be controlled through constructor parameters and how the values can be accessed. [28]

```

1 lif = hxsnn.LIF(
2     10,
3     ...,
4     enable_cadc_recording=True,
5     enable_spike_recording=True,
6     enable_madc_recording=True,
7     record_neuron_id=0 # which neuron to record with MADC

```

```

8 )
9
10 o = lif(synapse_output)
11
12 o.current # input current from synapses
13 o.membrane_cadc # membrane potential measured with CADC
14 o.membrane_madc # membrane potential measured with MADC
15 o.spikes # spikes of the neurons

```

Listing 5: Recording neuron values with hxtorch

4.3.5 Size Of The System

Next to the discussed restrictions when interacting with the hardware, the size of the hardware itself also presents a challenge. The chip only contains 512 neurons with 256 incoming synapses each [68], which limits the possible size of networks. Using weighted connections limits the possible incoming synapses to 128. [38]

This limitation can be overcome through partitioning the network and combining neuron circuits. Based on work from Arnold et al., [31] presents how a feedforward network can be partitioned into subnetworks which are simulated sequentially on the hardware. Additionally, it shows how hxtorch supports compartment neurons, so the combination of multiple neuron circuits to one big neuron circuit. This bigger circuit supports a higher number of input connections, because it is connected to more input columns in the synapse matrix.

4.4 Early-Exit On BrainScaleS-2

The previous section highlighted restrictions of the system, presenting limitations of the size of possible networks as well as observables which can be recorded from the neurons and therefore used for training.

This section will discuss how this affects the feasibility of the early-exit strategies presented in the SotA and which software access is suitable for the implementation.

Many of the intricacies of the hardware can be solved through careful implementation. Utilising the provided calibration for the system is crucial to minimise the effect of the fixed-pattern noise. The small temporal misalignments have to be accepted. The limited resolution for the SNN' weights can also be overcome in software, using the functions provided by hxtorch to ensure that the weights stay in bounds.

Code exists also for the presented scaling of the membrane potential. So again, this complicates the implementation but can be solved in software.

PyNN presents more restrictions than hxtorch in terms of the available observables which can be recorded from the neurons. The presented early-exit strategies do not solely rely on the spikes, but often use the membrane potential [17; 55; 89]. Therefore, this work will use hxtorch for the model training.

A common challenge in the presented early-exit strategies is the interpretation of the neuron's states at various timesteps and the interpretation as output signal. Especially early, it is likely that no spikes happened yet. SEENN utilises the "stored accumulated output" from the network [55]. SNNCutoff sums the ratio of the current membrane potential to the neuron's threshold and the count of past spikes in order to capture past and possible future spiking [89]. TET loss uses Leaky Integrate (LI) neurons at the output layer, which naturally aggregate all past incoming signals, because they get aggregated in the sum of the membrane potential and do not get lost in the form of spikes and reset [17]. BrainScaleS supports all three approaches. Unlike PyNN, hxtorch allows the recoding of spikes as well as the neuron's membrane potentials for each timestep. The hardware also supports disabling the AdEx properties and spiking of the neuron to simplify the neuron model to LI [37].

The predictive set used by SpikeCP can also be accessed on BrainScaleS, because the model implemented in hxtorch can output spikes as well as membrane potential for each output neuron and each timestep. Therefore, all necessary information to determine the predictive set are available during training. During inference, these information can be read out by the PPU s.

The two-step approaches implemented by the decision-making agent in Dynamic Confidence and the policy-network in SEENN-2 are more difficult to implement on BrainScaleS. For training, both PyNN and hxtorch allow the execution of arbitrary python code during the forward pass. However, for inference those decision-making agents would need to run on the PPU s, so implemented in C++. While they support powerful computation, as shown by an experiment that used the PPU s to simulate an environment for a bee to fly through [68], the additional complexity of not only the implementation of a two-step approach, but doing it in two languages, exceeds the scope of this thesis but could be explored in the future.

As mentioned, the small size of the system can be compensated by partitioning the SNN. The sequential simulation of the partitions can work well with early-exit like it is done in ANNs: Subsequent layers are only simulated if a decision could not be made by the earlier ones. One could implement an exit layer at the end of each partition, allowing to stop after a subset of the partitions for easy examples, while the whole SNN - larger than the chip - can be utilised for complex examples.

However, this approach would add additional complexity, as next to only implementing early-exit, it also needs to be combined with the partitioning. Therefore, this is out of scope for this thesis, but should be considered as a possible follow-up for future work.

This thesis will implement a smaller model, which restricts the complexity of possible tasks the model can solve.

The challenging part is the continuous calculation of the model's confidence and the stopping of the inference.

BrainScaleS is implemented in a partly analog manner [68]. This means that unlike in software simulators, one cannot easily press pause during the simulation and continue where it stopped. Instead, the membrane potentials of the neurons as well as sent spikes continue to evolve.

Therefore, a major challenge which needs to be solved in this thesis is to implement the

early-exit pattern as used in SotA: Run the model until it is confident enough. Or in other words: Continuously observe the network's activity in hardware to determine how confident the model is and stop the inference early when the model is confident enough, in parallel to the computation happening in the analog circuits.

Neither PyNN nor hxtorch support this out of the box. Both are intended to run the model for a fixed duration, after which the hardware is reset. The measured observables are only returned from the hardware to the host after the run on the hardware finished [61]. Access during the runtime is possible with custom C++ code running on the PPU. Stopping the run early based on information collected during the runtime was not done before. Solutions for the access and early stopping will be discussed in the chapter on implementation.

In summary, BrainScaleS as analog hardware requires some care in the interaction. The translation between software and hardware must be considered and a match between both needs to be ensured. The diverse software stack allows a flexible choice of abstraction and different granularities in terms of available observables, which makes all required information for the early-exit approaches available.

Access to the system at different layers of abstraction will be utilised by using Python during the training with hxtorch. C++ code on the PPU will be used to implement the continuous observation and early-exit during inference.

Chapter 5

Implementation - Model Training

This chapter presents the implemented SNN, covering the chosen task, model design, loss and regularisation, as well as the training results and a comparison between the different approaches.

The inference is covered in the next chapter.

5.1 Task

The implemented SNN is a classifier, trained on the Yin-Yang dataset [51].

Each sample in the dataset is made up from a x- and y-coordinate in the range from 0.0 to 1.0. As shown in Fig. 11, each such point either belongs to the class Yin, Yang or Dot. In the original paper, the two input coordinates are encoded as spike-times for four input neurons. Two receiving a timed spike based on x and y, and the other two based on 1-x and 1-y. Despite the small size of the problem, Kriener et al. show that the task is not easy to learn. Comparing a model with working backpropagation, a shallow network without hidden layer, and a network with frozen hidden weights, only the first one is able to properly learn the round borders between the classes, especially in the middle of the symbol. [51]

This dataset is therefore a suitable choice for this thesis. It is small enough to easily fit on the BrainScaleS chip, even with a large hidden layer. The model's output can be visualised nicely, making it easy to detect whether the model is able to properly learn the necessary shapes without having to solely rely on the measured accuracy.

Additionally, the Yin-Yang symbol clearly contains easier and harder parts. Dots with an y-coordinate above 0.75 and below 0.25 could be correctly classified based on linear separation of the classes. The dots as well as the round border between Yin and Yang through the middle of the symbol is clearly harder to classify, because there is no linear separation between them.

It can therefore be assumed that early-exit can happen especially soon for samples from the outer areas, with a large distance to the other classes, while points in the inner area at

the border between classes need a longer runtime until the model comes to a confident prediction. This assumption is visualised in Fig. 12.

Figure 11: Samples from the Yin-Yang dataset, one color per class, based on [51]

Figure 12: Black areas mark assumed high suitability for early-exit. Based on [51]

5.2 Baseline Model

The Electronic Vision(s) team provides a tutorial how to train a model for the classification of the Yin-Yang dataset [39], which is used as a base for the implementation.

Using the tutorial provides multiple advantages. The notebook from the example can easily be used to train a reference model without including any form of early-exit. This model serves as baseline to measure the effects the different training approaches have. Reusing much of the code from the example also allows a focus on the implementation on the early-exit in training and later during inference, allowing to invest more time into these areas.

This section will briefly describe the structure of the tutorial's model and training which was also used by the this thesis, before the additions from this work are presented in the next section.

The baseline model has three layers, an output layer with three neurons, a hidden layer with 120 neurons and an input layer with a variable number of neurons. [39]

Choosing the size of 120 for the hidden layer was likely motivated by the results from Kriener et al., who showed that a model with a hidden layer of size 100 can be trained much faster and produce much more stable predictions than models with a hidden layer of size 10 or 30, while not being much worse than a model with a hidden layer of size 150 [51].

This leaves 133 neurons for the input layer. The tutorial adds a fifth input neuron, receiving a spike at a fixed bias-timestep. This is intended to increase the activity of the network. [39] As mentioned, SNNs rely on spikes to carry information, too little activity means no communication through the network. Fig. 13 shows the spike times of the five input neurons for three example coordinates.

Figure 13: Visualisation of input spike times, code based on [39]

During training, the model is run for 30 timesteps for each input sample, which equals 0.06 milliseconds. Afterwards, the highest membrane potential for each output neuron over the course of the runtime is determined and used as input for CE loss. The output layer uses LI neurons which are not able to spike.

The tutorial combines CE with a regularisation term for the average activation at the output layer. [39]

5.3 Changes For Early-Exit

Compared to the baseline model, this thesis changed the type of output neurons, the loss, added regularisation terms and changed the training to different runtimes like proposed by TIT.

To be able to compare the effects of these changes, multiple models were trained. Some only using TIT with various runtimes, and some also the different loss. This section introduces all changes for early-exit, before the next section shows which changes were used for which model and how they compare.

5.3.1 Output Neurons

The output neurons were changed to Integrate-and-Fire neurons. Their activation was calculated like described by Wu et al. for SNNCutoff: Summing up the number of past spikes and the current membrane potential divided by the spiking threshold of the neuron [89]. This results in a decimal number where the fractional part accurately describes how close the neuron is to the next spike.

This change was chosen to make the model fully spiking, enabling further extension by e.g. adding a layer behind the current output or feeding the output into another network like done in SEENN-2.

The combination of spikes and membrane potential leads to a differentiable value because

the membrane potential evolves continuously. As the fractional part grows closer to 1.0 before a spike, there are no sudden high jumps in the activation.

The leak was removed with the goal of preventing negative activations, which would make the values more friendly for the computation of the regularisation terms. However, spikes from the hidden layer with negative weights can still lead to negative activations.

The change was still kept, because the model’s activation can be nicely interpreted as the model accumulating confidence for a class and receiving evidence against a class, so negatively weighted spikes from the hidden layer, when it is rising or falling, respectively.

Listing 1 shows the calculation of the activation based on the number of past spikes `spikes` and the membrane potential `membrane_cadc`. `bss_threshold` is the hardware value for the spiking threshold of the neuron, `trace_scale` is the factor needed to translate between hardware and software.

```
1 fractions = (membrane_cadc / (bss_threshold * trace_scale))
2 return torch.cumsum(spikes, dim=0) + fractions
```

Listing 1: Calculate activation of a neuron based on past spikes and membrane potential

5.3.2 Loss

Two different losses were used. First, like in the baseline model, CE loss was used with the maximum activation over the simulation time per output neuron as input.

Alternatively, TET loss [17] receives the activations for each timestep and output neuron as input. Equation 7 shows the formula based on the paper. The loss calculates the CE per timestep instead of an aggregated value over the whole runtime and includes a regularization term with MSE.

$$L_{TET} = \frac{1}{T} \sum_{t=1}^T L_{CE}[O(t), y] \quad (7)$$

```
1 # input: tensor (batch_size, time_length, population_size)
2 loss_es = 0
3 ce_loss_fun = torch.nn.CrossEntropyLoss()
4 for t in range(input.size(0)):
5     loss_es += ce_loss_fun(input[t, ...], target)
6 loss_es = loss_es / input.size(0)
7
8 lambd: float = 0.001
9 phi = 1.0
10
11 mse_loss_fun = torch.nn.MSELoss()
12 y = torch.zeros_like(input).fill_(phi)
13 loss_mse = mse_loss_fun(input, y)
14
15 return (1 - lambd) * loss_es + lambd * loss_mse
```

Listing 2: Calculation inside forward function of TET loss, adapted from [18]

5.3.3 Regularization

Next to correctly classifying the samples, trained through backpropagating the described losses, the model must learn how to perform the classification.

Specifically, three of these "how"s need to be learned: energy-efficient, fast and confident. Each of these is controlled via its own regularization term.

As shown in listing 3, energy-efficiency is encouraged by adding the average number of spikes in the hidden layer, as well as the average output activation. Both terms are taken from the tutorial implementation.

Squaring the values has multiple benefits: Differences are exponentially emphasised, providing a stronger signal to the model. Additionally, negative values are eliminated, preventing the regularisation term from reducing the loss.

```

1 reg = torch.tensor(0., device=self.scores.device)
2
3 reg += factor_energy_efficiency_hidden * torch.mean(torch.sum(self.
4   network.s_h.spikes, dim=1) ** 2.)
5 reg += factor_energy_efficiency_output * torch.mean(self.scores ** 2)

```

Listing 3: Regularisation for energy-efficiency

The terms for energy-efficiency are needed to counteract the terms for speed and confidence which both lead the model towards increasing the strength of its output signal.

The regularisation term for speed is based on SNNCutoff [89]. It is only calculated for the correct samples per batch because it trains the model to increase the membrane potential. This would have a negative effect when done for wrong predictions, as the error would get emphasised and the neurons for the correct classes would need to reach a higher activation to surpass it.

The formula from the paper on SNNCutoff can be summarised as follows, $O(t)$ being the model's output at time t , and $\tilde{O}(t - N)$ the average output in the time from $t - N$ to t .

$$L_{SNNCutoff} = \frac{1}{T} \sum_t \cos_sim(O(t), \tilde{O}(t - N)) \quad (8)$$

Based on the implementation provided by the SNNCutoff paper, this thesis calculates the similarity of the neuron's activation to the max of the last timesteps. The parameter `lookback_timesteps` controls the number of timesteps to look back.

SNNCutoff uses the mean. The max instead of the mean was chosen for this thesis, because the neuron's membrane potentials, and therefore their output activations, can decrease when spikes with negative weights arrive. Using the mean could therefore lead to an average that is lower than the activation from the wrong output neurons, especially for points which are hard to classify and short runtimes where no spiking happens. Using the max prevents this from happening, nudging the model to keep the activation from the correct neuron higher than the others. Additionally, the value of the regularisation term is higher than with the mean, which increases its impact on the loss.

Listing 4 shows the implementation, `data_only_correct_neuron` contains the output activations for the output neuron that belongs to the correctly predicted class.

```

1 # activations from correct output neuron [ num_ts, batch_size ]
2 data_only_correct_neuron = ... # removed for simplification
3
4 max_vals, max_idx = data_only_correct_neuron.max(dim=0)
5 # build tensor only filled with max value per batch
6 max_tensor = max_vals.unsqueeze(0).expand_as(data_only_correct_neuron)
7
8 # select the values form the timesteps before the max occurred,
9 # up to lookback_timesteps back
10 time_idx = torch.arange(data_only_correct_neuron.size(0)).unsqueeze(1)
11 ts_before_max = (time_idx <= max_idx.unsqueeze(0)) \
12     & (time_idx > (max_idx.unsqueeze(0) - lookback_timesteps))
13
14 # cosine sim between activation from timesteps before max & max
15 cosine_sims = torch.nn.functional.cosine_similarity(
16     data_only_correct_neuron * ts_before_max,
17     max_tensor * ts_before_max,
18     dim=0, eps=1e-8
19 )
20
21 reg += self.reg_params.factor_speed * 1 / torch.mean(cosine_sims.abs())

```

Listing 4: Regularisation for speed

Lastly, a regularization term for the confidence was added. This is based on the approach used by SNNCutoff [89] which compare the highest and second highest output to perform a cutoff (so early-exit) during inference. A static confidence threshold was chosen, mainly because of the simplicity of its implementation.

Listing 5 shows the calculation. The difference between the highest and second highest output activation is calculated and compared to the desired threshold, given by `confidence_threshold`. A value close to the threshold or above is interpreted as signal that the model is very confident in its prediction, which results in a value close to zero for the regularisation term.

As for the speed regularisation, the confidence regularisation is also only applied for correctly classified examples. The intent behind this is that the model should first focus on the correctness, before the confidence is added. A low confidence in a correct prediction is ok, a high confidence in a wrong prediction not.

```

1 # activations from all output neurons [ num_ts, batch_size, 3 ]
2 scores_correct_entries = ... # removed for simplification
3
4 diff_highest_to_second = torch.diff(torch.topk(
5     scores_correct_entries, k=2, dim=1).values, dim=1).abs()
6 diff_to_confidence = (confidence_threshold - diff_highest_to_second)
7 diff_to_confidence.clamp(min=0) # overconfidence is fine
8
9 reg += factor_confidence * torch.mean(diff_to_confidence)

```

Listing 5: Regularisation for confidence

5.3.4 Runtime

In addition to the changes to the model and regularization, the training loop was also adapted. Using the approach proposed by Deng et al., most models were trained for different runtimes, ranging from short to long. Deng et al. combine this Time Inheritance Training with TET loss, because TET loss is able to optimise the model's output at each timestep, independent of the total duration of the training [17]. This thesis also uses this combination for one model.

For other models, the above regularization terms are combined with TIT for the training. The regularisation terms aim towards the same goal of early confidence as TET, which is why a comparison of both was done.

The motivation for early-exit is that the model is able to learn simple samples even when simulated for a short runtime. Gradually increasing the runtime with TIT lets the model extend its knowledge, learning the harder samples during the longer runtimes. This approach shows similarities to curriculum learning [82]. The model implicitly finds easier examples, because they are the ones that can be correctly classified by using only a fraction of the input spikes.

The only necessary change to the training loop was an extra loop for the runtimes and epochs, this is shown in Listing 6. RUNTIMES contains relative runtimes, e.g. 0.25 or 0.5.

```

1 for runtime_relative, num_epochs in zip(RUNTIMES, EPOCHS):
2     runtime = T_SIM * runtime_relative
3     runtime_timesteps = int(runtime / DT)
4
5     # change length of input spikes tensor -> needs to match the runtime
6     model.encoder._seq_length = runtime_timesteps
7     model.network.set_runtime(runtime_timesteps) # hxtorch.run(...)
8
9     for epoch in range(0, num_epochs + 1):
10        # Train & Test

```

Listing 6: Training for different runtimes

5.4 Model Training And Results

As mentioned, a few models were trained in this thesis with the goal to compare the effect of TIT, the different regularisation terms and TET on the accuracy, the early-exit timestamps and the training itself.

This section provides an overview of the models as well as the measured data that will be used to discuss the models in detail in the next section. All figures will be used for more detailed discussions later, so only a short explanation is provided for now.

The training happened with the hardware in the loop, so the actual analog circuits were used for the neurons and synapses. The analog membrane potentials were measured by the ADCs, provided to the Python interface and could be used with hxtorch there. This inclusion of the hardware was fully managed by hxtorch, no special implementation was necessary.

Accuracy and loss were measured for each epoch. Additionally, a scatterplot detailing the possible early-exit timestep and output activation traces for some example points were measured at the end of each notebook run. This information will be used in this section to compare the models.

Table 5.1 shows an overview of the different models that were trained.

As example, the model *TIT* was trained with CE loss, both regularisation terms for early-exit with a factor of 0.0004 and 0.0012, as well as regularisation for confidence and speed both with a factor of 0.0008. The model was first trained for three epochs with 50% of the original runtime of 60 microseconds. After those three epochs, it achieved an accuracy of 87.71. Afterwards, it was trained for two epochs with the full runtime, correctly classifying 91.52% of the test samples at the end, after five epochs in total.

Model	Loss	Regularisation	Epochs, learning rate & runtime	Accuracy %
Baseline	CE - MaxOT	eeh: 0.0 eoo: 0.0004 c: 0.0 s: 0.0	3 x 0.004 x 1.0	89.05
TIT-Static	CE - MaxOT	eeh: 0.0004 eoo: 0.0012 c: 0.0008 s: 0.0008	2 x 0.008 x 1.0 2 x 0.004 x 1.0	81.33 84.48
TIT	CE - MaxOT	eeh: 0.0004 eoo: 0.0012 c: 0.0008 s: 0.0008	3 x 0.008 x 0.5 2 x 0.008 x 1.0	87.71 91.52
TIT-0.25	CE - MaxOT	eeh: 0.0004 eoo: 0.0012 c: 0.0008 s: 0.0008	3 x 0.008 x 0.25 3 x 0.008 x 0.5 2 x 0.004 x 1.0	56.67 86.67 73.52
TIT-0.25-longer	CE - MaxOT	eeh: 0.0004 eoo: 0.0012 c: 0.0008 s: 0.0008	3 x 0.008 x 0.25 6 x 0.008 x 0.5 4 x 0.004 x 1.0	56.86 90.19 88.67
TET-TIT	TET loss	eeh: 0.0004 eoo: 0.0012 c: 0.0008 s: 0.0	3 x 0.008 x 0.5 4 x 0.008 x 1.0	79.33 84.29

Table 5.1: Overview of the different models which were trained. The accuracy was measured after the epochs in the corresponding row. Epochs were trained from top to bottom.

Regularisation: eeh / eoo = early-exit in hidden / output layer, c: confidence, s: speed.

All implementations shared a `confidence_threshold` of 0.8 for the confidence regularisation and 5 `lookback_timesteps` for the speed regularisation. The factors for the regularisation

terms and learning rates were determined separately, picking the overall best performing values for all models to keep them comparable. The idea to decrease the learning rate for the longer epochs was taken from TIT [17]. This reduction can prevent the model from adapting previously learned patterns too strongly, forgetting learned information.

The *Baseline* model is the one trained with the code from the tutorial. The model is trained for the full runtime for all epochs. It learns quickly, reaching 89.05 % accuracy after the third epoch. However, it is neither trained for confidence nor early-exit. The other models differ in the runtimes per epoch, so the use of TIT, the used loss and the number of epochs per runtime.

The following Fig. 14 provides an overview about the measured loss and accuracy for the models over different epochs and runtimes. It will be referred to when discussing the different models in detail below.

Using the model *TIT* as example again, marked with the red line in both plots, it can be seen that the model was not trained for 25% of the original runtime. The model starts at 0.5-0, so 50% of the original runtime. Before any training, the model achieves an accuracy of 34%. After training for one epoch, its accuracy rises to 81% at 0.5-1, then 86% at 0.5-2 after two epochs, and finally 87.71% after training for all three epochs at 50% of the original runtime. The model was then run for the full runtime at 1-0. Without any additional training, its accuracy dropped to 63%. After training one epoch at the full runtime, the accuracy steeply increased to 89% at 1-1 and finally 91.52% after training for both epochs at the full runtime.

The loss can be read similarly. $x-0$ always being the accuracy at runtime x before any training for that runtime, $x-1$ after training for the first epoch with runtime x .

Generally, some increase of the loss and decrease of the accuracy is expected when switching from epochs with shorter runtimes to longer ones. On the one hand, this is caused by more input spikes arriving at the model, which can trigger more spikes at the hidden layer and therefore change the signal at the output layer. Depending on the learned weights this can change the model's prediction, especially for difficult points at the class borders where output activations are similar for all classes, possibly decreasing the accuracy.

The increase in loss is then caused by new incorrect predictions. A small impact also comes from the regularisation terms for the early-exit, because they are not normalised over the time and accumulate more signal the longer the runtime.

Figure 14: Model loss and accuracy over the different epochs. Coloured areas cover epochs with the same runtime, so e.g. 0.5-4 is the 4th epoch with a runtime of 0.5. Models were trained for n epochs per runtime, where n can be 0. The 0th epoch per runtime was measured before the first training on that runtime. A "x" marks a point where loss and accuracy was measured for the model.

Fig. 15 visualises the time that each model needs to make a confident prediction during inference. It was created by running inference on 2.000 examples and plotting the timestamp when the model reached a confidence of 0.8. If the model was never confident, the maximum timestep of 30, so 60 microseconds of runtime, was used.

As example, the model *TIT* correctly classifies and reaches a confidence of 0.8 after 8 timesteps for the point $x=0.5, y=1$ at the top of the symbol. The right Dot area around $x=0.75$ and $y=0.5$ was also correctly classified and suitable for early-exit, with timesteps between 10 and 15, so half the full inference time. A few points at the left edge of the symbol at $x=0$ and $y=0.5$ were wrongly classified and the wrong prediction happened very quickly, after only 7 timesteps. The border between Yin and Yang as well as around the dots was difficult for the model, most wrong examples in the right plot are from that area. Additionally, early-exit was barely possible in the middle area of the symbol, visible by the early-exit timestep being 30 for most of the points there, correct and wrong.

Figure 15: Scatterplots highlighting the possible timestep for early-exit for correct and wrong examples per model. The redder, the earlier. Dark blue means that the model was not confident.

Lastly, Fig. 16 provides a more detailed look at the output of the models for four example points. The first two points from the left are the centres of both Dots in the Yin-Yang symbol. The point $x=0.25, y=0.9$ is located at the top left corner and belongs to class Yang, the rightmost point is part of class Yin and located at the bottom right of the symbol. All should be suitable for early-exit, because they have a high distance to the borders between classes.

Each row shows the output score, so activation, for all three output neurons of one model. Each column covers one example point, so that the early-exit timesteps can be easily compared. The red line belongs to Yang, blue to Yin and green to the output neuron for the Dot class. A black vertical line marks the timestep where the model reached a confidence of 0.8.

Figure 16: Traces for the models output activations for four example points. Colours of the traces match the colour of the Yin-Yang class, a vertical black line marks timesteps for early-exit (0.8 confidence), bold outlines mark the earliest early-exit per column.

Now that the data to compare the models, the losses, the effect of TIT and the regularisation terms was introduced, the insights from the different models will be presented. Model names are written in *italic*, so *TIT* is the model, TIT is Time Inheritance Training.

5.4.1 Speed And Confidence Regularisation

The model *TIT-Static* uses the same CE loss as the *Baseline* model and was also only trained for the full runtime. Different to the *Baseline*, it adds the regularisation terms for speed and confidence, as well as more energy-efficiency regularisation.

While, the accuracy of the model is 4.6% worse than the *Baseline*, the effect of the regularisation terms can be seen. In Fig. 16, the activations for *TIT-Static* are higher and increase much steeper than for the *Baseline*. early-exit is possible for three of the points, compared to zero. The difference between the correct and wrong output neurons is exactly what the confidence regularisation intends to achieve. The steepness is promoted by the speed regularisation.

This suggests that the regularisation terms have the desired effect, but also hints towards more epochs being needed to increase the accuracy to the same level as the *Baseline*. This is expected, as the regularisation terms add an additional target for the model, which it needs to balance with the plain loss.

5.4.2 Effect Of TIT

The model *TIT-Static* suggests that the regularisation works as intended. With the goal of even quicker early-exit, the model *TIT* changes the first three epochs from the full runtime to only half. To keep the effect measurable, nothing else is changed between both models.

The change increases the accuracy by 7%. While the model *TIT* was trained for 1 more epoch in sum, Fig. 14 supports the assumption that this is not the reason for the difference in accuracy, because it was consistently more accurate than *TIT-Static*, even in epoch 1-1.

The traces in Fig. 16 show that *TIT* has earlier timestamps where early-exit can be performed for all four points. This effect is also visible for all 2,000 points in the testset in Fig. 15, where *TIT* can early-exit significantly more than the *Baseline*, which does not early-exit at all. The goal of TIT, achieving correct predictions as early as possible, was therefore achieved.

Additionally, the model may have benefitted from its knowledge gained during the shorter runtime. The evolution of the accuracy in Fig. 14 shows that *TIT* already steadily achieved a high accuracy for the epochs with a runtime of 0.5, which it was able to carry into the full runtime, where its accuracy increased similarly steep as the one of *TIT-Static*, but at a higher value.

5.4.3 Shorter First Epochs

The last comparison showed that using TIT with half and the full runtime has a positive effect on the timestep for early-exit as well as the model's accuracy. The model *TIT-0.25* was trained to investigate whether an even shorter runtime for the first epochs could lead to stronger positive effects.

Remarkably, 57 % of the test data could be classified correctly when the model was only running for 25 % of the full runtime. Putting the runtime into perspective with the input spike times, as in Fig. 13, one can see that the model mostly receives information for x and y values at the outer edges of the symbol.

The scatterplot of early-exit timesteps for the model after only training for 0.25 runtime in Fig. 17, supports this observation. The edges of the Yin-Yang symbol can be classified correctly, quickly, and even confidently within the first quarter of the whole runtime, while the middle of the symbol is classified late and wrongly often.

Interestingly, the tips of Yin-Yang, at the upper right and lower left, are also incorrect, even though they have coordinates at the edges. This could be explained by their higher difficulty because points for Yin and Yang lie in close proximity here. The model therefore misses spikes which provide more evidence over time, i.e. caused by the inverse of the coordinates, which would have happened after a quarter of the runtime.

Figure 17: Scatterplots highlighting the possible timestep for early-exit for correct and wrong examples for the model $TIT-0.25$ after only training for 3 epochs with 0.25 runtime.

Overall, the model $TIT-0.25$ achieved a worse accuracy and even drastically decreased in accuracy after training on the full runtime. Additionally, looking at Fig. 16 again, the timesteps for early-exit were slightly improved in two cases, but much worse for another example.

A possible explanation for the reduced accuracy can be that $TIT-0.25$ learned patterns during the shorter runtimes which did not all translate well into the full runtime. This assumption is supported by Fig. 14 where the accuracy for $TIT-0.25$ decreased much more than for TIT at the first epoch for the full runtime. It can be seen that training for more epochs with 0.5 runtime for the model $TIT-0.25-longer$ reduces the loss in accuracy, while keeping the improvement in terms of early-exit for the four example points. Therefore, it seems plausible that the additional shorter epochs call for additional epochs with longer runtime to give the model time to translate the patterns learned during the short runtime into ones that work for the full runtime.

5.4.4 TET Loss

All models covered so far used the CE loss also used in the example. The final model replaces it with TET loss. TET loss calculates the CE loss for each timestep and averages the result over the time. Therefore, the goal of early-exit is included in the loss function, which is why the factor for the speed regularisation was set to 0, as these would be two signals for the same goal, possibly hiding the effect of TET.

The model trained with TET loss achieved the worst accuracy of all models. But also the earliest timesteps for early-exit, highlighted with the bold outlines in Fig. 16 and visible in the bottom right scatterplot in Fig. 15. The positive effect on the early-exit can be explained with the structure of the TET loss: The model is trained to be correct at each timestep, which implies that the activation for the correct output neuron must be higher than for the other neurons. The additional confidence regularisation pushes these higher activations to be high enough for early-exit.

Looking at the struggle of the *TET-TIT* model to properly recognise the Yin-Yang shape in Fig. 15, one must wonder whether there is a bug in the implementation that prevents the model from properly learning. Looking at the scatterplot, the dots can be clearly separated from the other classes. This clear separation of the dot classes was not achieved by a model with broken backpropagation tested in the original paper on the Yin-Yang dataset [51]. Unit tests for the loss function were also written, one can therefore assume that a bug is not the cause for the problematic learning.

One possible reason could be the mixed goals of the loss function. It puts a much stronger emphasis on the correctness for every timestep, which means that the model can reduce the loss by increasing the membrane potential for simple points quicker instead of learning the harder areas of the symbol. This is also true for the regularisation term for speed, but the small factor used for it means that it has a much smaller impact compared to TET loss.

This misalignment between loss and accuracy is also visible in Fig. 14 where the big decrease in accuracy at epoch 1-1 increases the loss for the model *TET-TIT* way less compared to the other models. Overall, the loss is much higher. In essence, it applies speed regularisation with a factor of 1 instead of 0.0008, which explains the high value. Due to the natural dynamics of the neurons and the fact that the first input spike does not arrive at timestep zero, the CE will always be high for the first few timesteps. The possible minimum for the loss is therefore higher than for the CE used by the other models.

5.5 Summary

Overall, training a model for early-exit was successful. Both, the regularisation terms and TET loss lead to models which can significantly reduce the inference time. While the possibility for early-exit was improved, the accuracy for *TIT-0.25* and *TET-TIT* were worse than for the model *TIT*.

A conflict between accuracy and early-exit is possible: Withholding information during the very short early epochs improves early-exit, but removes information from the model which it needs for accurate predictions.

It is worth to note that the goal of this chapter was not to train models with the highest accuracy possible. Instead, the number of epochs were kept similar to make the comparison between the models and for the effect of the losses and regularisations as fair as possible. All models still showed improvements during the last epochs, which is visible in Fig. 14. It is therefore plausible that further training for more epochs - not only for the full runtime, but also half, where the models already achieved a very good accuracy - will increase the accuracy further.

Visible over all models was support for the initial assumption for the suitability of early-exit for different areas of the Yin-Yang symbol. Fig. 15 shows that most blue or wrong areas are around the dots or the edges of the Yin-Yang symbol, while early-exit can be performed very well at the upper and lower edges.

As assumed, BrainScaleS as hardware did not limit the implementation. However, the limited available memory of the Jupyter instances made training for many epochs a bit difficult because of necessary restarts after every two epochs for the full runtime to avoid running out of memory. This could also have affected the accuracy slightly negatively, but was the same for all models.

Losses could use not only the spikes, but also frequently sampled membrane potentials. The activation as decimal with spikes and membrane potential ratio could be easily calculated. The baseline implementation from the tutorial allowed a simple replacement of the functions to change.

Debugging on the Jupyter Instance was limited, so debugging and testing of loss and regularisation were done locally by writing unit tests and using output activations exported from the Jupyter Notebook to debug the functions and ensure that the correct tensor dimensions are used.

Chapter 6

Implementation - Inference

This chapter investigates how the early stopping during the inference can be implemented on BrainScaleS. First, the general flow of running code on BrainScaleS is presented before going into the detail of the necessary adjustments for the support of early-exit.

The model TIT from the last chapter is used for inference. It is worse than TET-TIT in terms of the earliness of the early-exit timesteps, but has a better accuracy. It still only needs a fraction of the runtime to correctly classify many examples, so early-exit during inference can be applied often.

This chapter describes the inference with hxtorch. Inference with PyNN was attempted but not successful because of issues with the translation from the network in hxtorch to PyNN. The attempt is briefly described in appendix A.

However, the general approach to early-exit described in the following could be also used with PyNN because it is independent of the network itself.

6.1 How BrainScaleS Executes A Run

As seen in earlier parts of this thesis, the end user can write their code to interact with BrainScaleS in Jupyter Notebooks in Python. The Python code can be used to define the network structure, the observables to monitor at the neurons and synapses, all parameters for the analog circuits, the runtime on the hardware and also code which should be executed directly on the chip. This is the configuration for the system, visible as black box in the Host-row in Fig. 18.

During runtime, the Python layer quickly hands off to the C++ libraries of BrainScaleS, starting with `grenade`, the library for GRaph-based Experiment Notation And Data-flow Execution [33].

`grenade` builds an execution graph based on the configuration for the system. Internally, it makes use of the flow-graph from Intel's `tbb` library [35; 50]. Basically, a graph consisting of different hardware entities, e.g. the routing crossbar for spikes, neurons, the synapse drivers, is built and spikes from neurons, measured observables from the CADCs and other events are routed between the hardware components. [74]

Fig. 18 shows this behaviour as parallel activity of the PPU, e.g. to collect the neuron’s membrane potentials, and the FPGA, e.g. to store the measured potentials in its local DRAM. At the end of the experiment, all information collected during the experiment are sent to the Host, where the end user can observe them in their Jupyter Notebook.

Figure 18: Involvement of Host, FPGA and PPU in the code execution. Black boxes signal the activity of the hardware component. Taken from [61]

The implementation of early-exit must solve two challenges:

If the run should be stopped early, accessing the observables after the experiment is too late. Instead, they need to be accessed during the experiment runtime.

The execution must be stopped based on the condition whether the confidence threshold was reached, instead of using a static runtime like `pynn.run(42)`. Therefore, the end of experiment in Fig. 18 must be determined dynamically, possibly stopping before all input spikes were processed.

These two challenges are examined in the following.

6.2 Observing Neurons And Synapses

The end user is not restricted to Python code. Instead, code for the embedded processors, so the PPU, can be written in C++ and passed to the experiment.

The code is then executed with a predefined schedule, allowing access to the observables in realtime.

Listing 1 shows the creation of a `PlasticityRule`. The `timer` controls the timing of the execution, which is defined in PPU clocks. The kernel, so the code that runs on the PPU, was written in a separate file. Parameters like `confidence_threshold` which are also needed in Python are replaced in the kernel code using Python’s `format` function. The kernel code will be covered in detail in the next section. After defining the timing and the code, the `PlasticityRule` can be added to a `Synapse` from the SNN.

```

1 plasticity_rule_output = grenade.network.PlasticityRule()
2
3 val = grenade.network.PlasticityRule.Timer.Value
4 plasticity_rule_output.timer.start = val(microseconds_to_ppu_clocks(0))
5 # period and num_periods do not matter, we use while(true)
6 plasticity_rule_output.timer.period = val(microseconds_to_ppu_clocks(4))
7 plasticity_rule_output.timer.num_periods = 4
8
9 with open("./inference_kernel_output.cpp", "r") as f:
10     kernel = f.read()
11
12 kernel = textwrap.dedent(kernel.format(
13     neuron_threshold=BSS2_THRESHOLD,
14     confidence_threshold=confidence_threshold,
15
16     neuron_row_on_dls=neuron_row_on_dls,
17     num_neurons=3,
18     neuron_column_array=",".join(str(x) for x in range(3)),
19
20     magic_address=magic_address,
21     magic_value=magic_value,
22 ))
23 plasticity_rule_output.kernel = kernel
24
25 # in the SNN:
26 self.linear_o = hxsnn.Synapse(
27     # ...
28     plasticity_rule=plasticity_rule_output
29 )

```

Listing 1: Definition of a PlasticityRule with code for the PPU

Listing 2 shows the main function of the PPU kernel. Double curly braces are used to enclose blocks because single curly braces contain the variables which are replaced by Python's string formatting, e.g. {neuron_row_on_dls}.

Connecting the plasticity rule to neurons or synapses provides an array of handles to the respective entity in the kernel, containing `NeuronViewHandles` and / or `SynapseArrayViewHandles`. `hxtorch` only supports the attachment of plasticity rules to synapses, so the array of `NeuronViewHandles` is always empty.

The confidence of the model should be observed continuously, which is implemented with `while(true)`. This could also be done through a very short period for the `PlasticityRule` timer, but the implementation through the loop is more robust because it does not depend on the exact timing for the scheduling.

When on the correct PPU, so the one that is connected to the hemisphere where the output neurons are placed, each iteration determines their activations, calculates the model's confidence and breaks out of the loop if the confidence is high enough. If the model is never confident, the loop ends shortly before the maximum desired runtime of 60 microseconds to prevent a timeout of the FPGA.

```

1 template <size_t N>
2 void PLASTICITY_RULE_KERNEL(
3     std::array<SynapseArrayViewHandle, N>& synapses,
4     std::array<NeuronViewHandle, 0>& /* neurons */)
5 {{

```

```

6   if (ppu != PPU0nDLS({neuron_row_on_dls})) {{
7       return;
8   }}
9
10  while (true) {{
11      if (now() - start_time >= nearly_60_us) {{
12          // store end results
13          break;
14      }}
15
16      for (uint8_t c = 0; c < {num_neurons}; ++c) {{
17          // calculate activations
18      }}
19      auto confidence = // calculate confidence
20
21      if ( confidence >= {confidence_threshold} ) {{
22          // store end results
23          break;
24      }}
25  }}
26
27  // code to signal "stop" to the FPGA
28  }}

```

Listing 2: Main loop on the PPU's

The placement of the output neurons is known because of a `placement_constraint`, which allows to place neurons at specific columns and rows, each row belongs to one PPU. The constraint used in the SNN is shown in Listing 3.

```

1 self.if_readout = IF(
2   # ...
3   placement_constraint=list(
4     halco.LogicalNeuronOnDLS(
5       hxsnn.morphology.SingleCompartmentNeuron(1).compartments,
6       halco.AtomicNeuronOnDLS(
7         halco.NeuronRowOnDLS(neuron_row_on_dls),
8         halco.NeuronColumnOnDLS(nrn)))
9   for nrn in range(n_out)))

```

Listing 3: Placement Constraint to control the position of neurons

6.3 Calculation Of Activations And Confidence

The trained model calculates the output activation as decimal with the number of past spikes as integer part and the fraction of current membrane potential and spike threshold as decimal part, an idea from SNNCutoff [89].

The implementation for inference had to apply some simplifications because the timing of the `PlasticityRule` proved to be challenging, this will be discussed in section 6.6 which covers the inference results. To reduce the number of necessary hardware access operations and calculation on the PPU and to keep the code as simple as possible, the confidence of the model is only determined based on the number of past spikes. The threshold is

increased to 1 instead of 0.8. This can lead to stopping even if the model would not have been confident during training, e.g. for activations 1.4 and 2.1, so one and two spikes respectively, but only 0.7 difference between activations when including the membrane potential fraction.

The empty array of `NeuronViewHandles` mentioned in the previous section presents a challenge, because the `NeuronViewHandle` has the method `get_rate_counter` to get the number of spikes of the neurons [34]. This functionality is needed, but not provided by the `SynapseArrayViewHandle`. To overcome this issue, the code used in the implementation of the `NeuronViewHandle` was copied to the `PlasticityRule`. Using the row and columns defined in the `placement_constraint` and passed to the `PlasticityRule` as the variables `neuron_row_on_dls`, `num_neurons` and `neuron_column_array`, an `AtomicNeuronOnDLS` is created. It identifies a single neuron on the chip. Its method `toSpikeCounterReadOnDLS` can be used to access the number of past spikes from this neuron. This code shows the logical abstraction, which is translated into the correct hardware access operations by the lower layers of the software stack.

Listing 4 shows the function to calculate the activation of the neurons. The code for `num_spikes_from_neuron` was taken from the `NeuronViewHandle`. The number of spikes is multiplied by ten to leave room for a possible later addition of the membrane potential fraction. The fraction would then be stored in the first number before the decimal point to avoid working with floats, as that is not natively supported by the PPU¹.

```

1 // neuron_view_handle.cpp#L19-L45
2 uint32_t num_spikes_from_neuron(uint8_t c) {{
3     // this works because of the placement_constraint to column 0-2.
4     NeuronColumnOnDLS const col(c);
5     auto const row = NeuronRowOnDLS(static_cast<uintmax_t>(ppu));
6     AtomicNeuronOnDLS const neuron = AtomicNeuronOnDLS(col, row);
7
8     auto const spike_counter_read = read<SpikeCounterRead>(neuron.
9     toSpikeCounterReadOnDLS());
10    return spike_counter_read.get_overflow() ? 0 : spike_counter_read.
11    get_count().value();
12 }}
13
14 uint32_t activation_for_neuron(uint8_t c) {{
15     return 10 * num_spikes_from_neuron(c);
16 }}
17
18 void PLASTICITY_RULE_KERNEL(...)
19 {{
20     // ...
21     while (true) {{
22         // ...
23         for (uint8_t c = 0; c < {num_neurons}; ++c) {{
24             activation = activation_for_neuron(c);
25         }}
26     }}
27 }}

```

Listing 4: Calculation of activation on the PPU, uses code from [34]

¹Information from personal correspondence with E. Müller; 27.02.2026

The activations are then used to calculate the confidence of the model. Listing 5 shows how the largest and second-largest activations are persisted while gathering the activations of the output neurons in the while-loop before calculating their difference as the model's confidence.

```

1 for (uint8_t c = 0; c < {num_neurons}; ++c) {{
2     activation = activation_for_neuron(c);
3
4     if (activation != 0) {{
5         if( activation > largest ) {{
6             second_largest = largest;
7             largest = activation;
8             predicted_class = c;
9         }}
10        else if ( activation > second_largest ) {{
11            second_largest = activation;
12        }}
13    }}
14 }}
15 auto confidence = largest - second_largest;

```

Listing 5: Calculation of confidence on the PPU

Next to the activations, the `predicted_class` is also updated during each iteration. It will be read by the FPGA at the end of the inference to avoid having to determine the model's prediction again in Python.

The next section presents how this access from the FPGA is possible.

6.4 Accessing Variables From The PPU

The PPU writes three variables when the model is confident or the runtime of nearly 60 microseconds was reached. The `time_result`, so the time spent in the loop, the `predicted_class`, as well as the model's `confidence_result` are stored. This is shown in Listing 6.

```

1 // outside of main loop
2 uint32_t time_result;
3 uint32_t confidence_result;
4 uint32_t predicted_class;
5
6 // within while(true)
7 if (now() - start_time >= nearly_60_us) {{
8     time_result = now() - start_time;
9     confidence_result = largest - second_largest; // < threshold
10    predicted_class = 42; // not a valid class
11 }}
12
13 if ( confidence >= {confidence_threshold} ) {{
14     confidence_result = confidence;
15     time_result = now() - start_time;
16 }}

```

Listing 6: Writing the final values for the variables on the PPU

Those variables contain valuable information, e.g. the exact time spent in the loop which could not be determined in Python. To access those variables, they can be defined as `readout_symbols` on the experiment, shown in Listing 7. The names defined here must exactly match the names in the PPU kernel.

After finishing, the values can then be accessed through the experiment. This was used to determine whether the implemented early-exit works and to gather the data for the results of this chapter.

```

1 # before run()
2 exp.default_execution_instance.read_ppu_symbols = {"confidence_result",
3           "time_result", "predicted_class"}
4
5 # after run()
6 read_symbol_names = exp.default_execution_instance.read_ppu_symbols
7 for _, ppu_symbols_read in exp.ppu_symbols_read[0].items():
8     for name in read_symbol_names:
9         symbol_data = ppu_symbols_read[grenade.common.ChipOnConnection(0)][
10            name].values()
11         for idx, data in enumerate(symbol_data):
12             print(f"{name}, {idx}: {[w.value.value() for w in data.words]}")

```

Listing 7: Accessing the variables from the PPU in Python

Now, the PPUs access the neuron’s observables in realtime to determine the model’s confidence and store the results. These results can be accessed after the experiment in Python. The last missing piece is the communication of the stop signal to the FPGA.

6.5 Early Stopping

If the confidence calculated above reaches the predefined threshold, the PPU should signal the FPGAs to stop the execution. The FPGA can access the PPU’s local SRAM. Therefore, the PPU will write a specific value to a specific predefined address in its SRAM, shown in Listing 8. The FPGA continuously polls the address and stops the execution when the value at the address matches the `magic_value`.²

```

1 volatile int* addr = reinterpret_cast<int*>({magic_address});
2 *addr = {magic_value};

```

Listing 8: Writing to the magic address at the PPU.

The logic on the FPGAs is implemented as a playback program. The playback program is not directly written. Instead, its logic can be configured in Python, shown in Listing 9. This configuration is then translated to a playback program by the libraries for BrainScaleS. Before starting the polling of the `magic_address`, the FPGA waits for the omnibus, the on-chip bus [61], to be idle [36]. Afterwards, the instruction timeout is increased for the following wait for the `magic_value`.

The wait happens through a `PollingOmnibusBlock`, which blocks until the address contains the defined target (or the timeout is reached) [36]. The `sram_bottom_base` is the global

²The idea for the communication via magic value at magic address is from E. Müller; personal communication, 16.01.2026

address of the SRAM from the bottom PPU. This is needed to properly address the `magic_address` in the global address space of the chip. The bottom PPU is needed because the `placement_constraint` selects neuron row one.

Lastly, the playback program is injected in the `realtime_end` section of the experiment. A realtime section refers to one block of time where the hardware evolves analogously, so without reconfiguration or breaks initiated by the host³. The injection of input spikes and the following spikes in the rest of the model therefore happens in one realtime section, the check for the `magic_value` happens after this is done.

```

1 builder = sta.PlaybackProgramBuilder()
2
3 # ensure pending omnibus operations are all done
4 builder.block_until(halco.BarrierOnFPGA(), hal.Barrier.omnibus)
5
6 # 1. increase FPGA instruction timeout to enable macroscopic runtimes
7 timeout = hal.InstructionTimeoutConfig()
8 timeout.value = microseconds_to_fpga_clocks(60) // 125 MHz
9
10 builder.write(halco.InstructionTimeoutConfigOnFPGA(), timeout)
11
12 # 2. define exit condition from an FPGA's view
13 # wait for the PPU to write a magic value to a magic address
14 poll_config = hal.PollingOmnibusBlockConfig()
15
16 sram_bottom_base = 0x03800000
17 poll_config.address = halco.OmnibusAddress(sram_bottom_base +
18     magic_address // 4)
19 poll_config.target = magic_value
20 poll_config.mask = 0xffffffff
21
22 builder.write(halco.PollingOmnibusBlockConfigOnFPGA(), poll_config)
23 builder.block_until(halco.PollingOmnibusBlockOnFPGA(), hal.
24     PollingOmnibusBlock())
25
26 # 3. attach the playback program to the experiment (exp)
27 exp.default_execution_instance.injection_inside_realtime_end = builder

```

Listing 9: Polling of the magic address at the FPGA. Code largely provided by E. Müller.

This works, because the graph-based execution with the mentioned `tbb-graph` first processes all input spikes, e.g. defined through a `Population` with predefined spike times, like shown in Listing 10. Then, if the runtime passed to `pynn.run()` or `hxtorch.snn.run()` is larger than the time for the latest input spike, the FPGA continues to wait until the full runtime is reached before collecting all observables and sending them to the host.

This waiting for x time after the input processing can be replaced by a wait until value x is present at memory location y .⁴

```

1 input_neurons = pynn.Population(30, pynn.cells.SpikeSourceArray(
2     spike_times=[1.2, 2.3, 2.8, 4.2]
3 ))

```

Listing 10: A PyNN-Population which sends input spikes at predefined times.

³Information from personal correspondence with E. Müller; 16.01.2026

⁴Information from personal correspondence with E. Müller; 16.01.2026

We now have all parts for early-exit inference: A model which is able to classify points very quickly, a plasticity rule to determine the confidence of the model from the output neurons and write the stop-signal for the FPGAs as well as a playback program to listen for the stop signal from the PPU.

The full code for the inference can be found in the additional resources. All parts relevant for early-exit were discussed in this section.

6.6 Results

To verify the functionality of the described implementation, inference was run on multiple examples. The points were picked to cover a range of difficulties and therefore early-exit timesteps. Fig. 19 shows the activation of the output neurons for these points as well as the results of the three PPU variables. 42 as predicted class is used when the model was not confident. The line color matches the color of the classes in the Yin-Yang symbol, Yang being red, Dots green and Yin blue.

The top row contains easy points, located at the upper left inside Yang, the lower right inside Yin and in the middle of the left Dot. The middle row contains harder points which are located closer to the tips of Yin and Yang, in the area where the other class is close. The bottom row contains points right on the border between Yin and Yang, which runs through the middle of the symbol. Again, the first timestep where the model reached the confidence threshold of 0.8 used during training is marked with a black vertical line. The PPU uses a different threshold of 10, equal to one spike.

Overall, it can be seen that the `time_result` is below 60 for all easy points and also for some of the more difficult ones. The code on the PPU is therefore able to correctly access the neuron's spike counts, calculate the confidence and end the execution.

The plot for $x=0.3,y=0.3$ highlights an inaccuracy which was accepted when implementing the simplified confidence calculation on the PPU. The model reaches a confidence of 0.8 based on the original calculation of the activation. With the implementation only based on spikes however, the predicted class is 42, so the confidence threshold of one spike was not reached.

The three plots in the top row show another issue with the timing. While the model was confident very quickly, after 15 to 20 μs , the `time_result` shows a value of around 50 μs . This is not caused by the difference in calculation, in all cases the correct class also has one spike more than the others after at most 20 μs . Rather, the code on the PPU seems to be delayed, only starting when the model already reached e.g. three spikes for $x=0.75,y=0.1$, which would mean a delay of roughly 30 μs . Same with the left and right plot in the row. The final number of spikes, two and one, were already present after 20 μs , but the written timestamp is much higher.

This issue was not consistently present with the same magnitude measured here. Especially, a restart of the BrainScaleS chip reduced the timing problems a lot. Other measured `time_results` were 28 and 32 for $x=0.75,y=0.1$ and 26 and 33 for $x=0.25,y=0.9$. The depicted `time_results` for these two points in Fig. 19 are close to twice as high as the observed minimum. Still, even 28 and 26 μs would hint towards a delay, the expected

Figure 19: Traces for the models output activations for the example points and PPU variables. Colours of the traces match the colour of the Yin-Yang symbol, black vertical lines mark the point where confidence reached 0.8.

`time_result` for the two points would be roughly $15 \mu\text{s}$.

This suggests that there is an underlying issue with the hardware or communication between FPGA and PPU and not within the implemented code.

It was attempted to measure the actual effect on throughput during inference. For that, inference was run with multiple batches of size 100 created by repeating either $x=0.9, y=0.1$, a very easy point, or $x=0.5, y=0.5$, a point where early-exit is not possible. Then, the passed time measured via `perf_counter` in Python was compared.

However, no difference could be measured. Theoretically, one would expect a speedup of $20 \mu\text{s}$ per batch entry, so 2ms per batch. However, the inference involves a multitude of operations, both in Python and on the chip: Coordinates must be encoded to spike times, the plasticity rule must be compiled and sent to the PPU, the connections between the host with the Jupyter Notebook, the FPGA and the PPU must be set up, and the results need to be collected back to the host. All these operations take much longer than $20 \mu\text{s}$, even few milliseconds are a factor of 10 to 100 times larger.

The variance between different runs of inference for batches with the same point was already magnitudes larger than the expected savings through early-exit, the difference was therefore too small to reliably measure it.

Still, the inference will be sped up if the polling configuration on the FPGA works, all other parts of the code are working. The FPGA would error if it did not see the `magic_value` before reaching its configured timeout. This error does not occur, so the communication via the `magic_address` works as intended.

Chapter 7

Discussion

Overall, this implementation attempted in this thesis was partly successful. The research questions were successfully explored, details could be tested further in future work.

The training of multiple models for early-exit successfully lead to models which can confidently early-exit for large areas of the Yin-Yang symbol. This thesis identified the combination of TET and TIT as most impactful to train for early-exit. The best combination of accuracy and early-exit was achieved by TIT with CE loss and regularisation terms for speed and confidence.

This thesis used the simplest approaches from the state of the art, only covering TET loss, TIT and regularisation terms. More complex approaches like the decision-making agent from Dynamic Confidence or a solution for partitioned networks were not explored and could be topic of further research. Especially a solution for partitioned networks would make it possible to add early-exit to larger networks on BrainScaleS while the current efforts towards a multi-chip solutions are still in progress. Additionally, further iteration on the hyperparameters and the number of training epochs can be done to evaluate the best possible performance - in terms of accuracy, as well as early-exit. The models trained in this thesis overall still showed improvements at the end of their training.

The possible early-exit timesteps showed that the runtime of the inference can be greatly reduced, saving time and energy during inference. However, as the trained models were trained for confidence, their output activations are higher than for the baseline model, which is visible for the example points in Fig. 16. This results in an increased energy-usage, because higher activations, so more spikes in this case, need to be transported across the chip and processed by the analog circuits. Overall, this counteracts the energy savings achieved with early-exit. A quantisation of the used energy could not be done within this thesis. One motivator behind the higher activations is the confident threshold, the selection of a smaller value for it could therefore reduce this issue.

The improved inference throughput stays however.

Thanks to the library hxtorch, the complexity of the training's implementation were the loss and the regularisation terms. The training itself as well as the access to the necessary neuron observables was not an issue.

The opposite was true for the early-exit during inference, which was much more challenging

than anticipated. The main source of problems was the fact that many moving parts are involved when working with a partly-analog hardware like BrainScaleS. Things that needed to be considered were the correct scaling of the neuron configuration and especially the correct timing for the plasticity rules. A translation from hxtorch to PyNN was attempted, but remained unsuccessful because of issues with the correct scaling of the neuron parameters.

While much of the implementation could be done in Python, the inference also made it necessary to write C++ code to directly interact with the neurons. With a lack of thoroughly explained examples on this low level of abstraction, a study of the actual implementation as well as multiple exchanges with one of the supervisors was necessary to be able to determine a way to implement the needed logic. This implementation happened on a lower level and required more expert-knowledge than assumed.

While it was challenging, the implementation was at least partly successful. The confidence of the model can be determined in real-time and be used to send a stop signal to the FPGA. However, the timing of the communication between the PPU and the FPGA is still a source for issues. All the timing issues were amplified by the very small initial runtime of the model. Changes of only a few μs could have been compensated when the full runtime would have been a few tens or hundreds of milliseconds. A longer-running task would have made the implementation much easier in this regard, future work could choose a different task than Yin-Yang.

While the learning curve to get familiar enough with the system to implement, debug and observe the implementation during training and inference was steep, this challenge put up by BrainScaleS was manageable. The unsolved issues in inference are most likely caused by the interaction between the different parts of the system. Debugging these issues within these thesis to a point where the cause can be exactly determined was not possible. However, as the separate parts work as planned, the issue must lie in the interaction between the components and the timing of the different programs on the PPU and FPGA.

Further work could continue the implementation in multiple ways. First, the communication between PPU and FPGA through a magic value at a magic address is risky, as one can not be sure that the selected address is not in use. The address should be selected in a safer way, ensuring that no relevant information is overwritten. Alternatively, a different communication of the stop signal could be explored, although it likely has to make use of the PPU's SRAM as means to communicate.

Also, the current implementation does not make use of all potential for early-exit.

Looking back at Fig. 15 which shows the timesteps for early-exit for the model TIT, we see that the upper and lower parts of the symbol can be correctly classified after around 8 timesteps. This equals 16 μs of absolute runtime. But the latest input spike for a coordinate value of 1.0 or 0.0 arrives after 40 μs of total runtime.

The current early-exit is only performed after the last input spike, which can save 20 μs of the total runtime, so a third. Exiting after 16 μs reduces the runtime by 73 %. Waiting for all input spikes to be processed therefore reduces the impact of early-exit a lot.

Further work should therefore investigate how input spikes can be added dynamically.

One possibility would be the use of a spike source on the PPU ¹, so with a plasticity rule like used in the current approach, but sending spikes instead of calculating the activation. However, the timing would be an even bigger issue here, as the input spikes need precise timing, especially at the borders between classes. A task where slight variances of the timing of the input spikes does not matter as much would be the better choice here. Rate coding could also be used to reduce the impact of differences in the timing of single spikes, the increased energy usage from the rate codes can then be counteracted by the early-exit.

Apart from the challenges, it should be highlighted that only a few adjustments to the software stack of BrainScaleS were necessary to make the implementation of the early-stopping possible, a feature that was never asked for before. These changes included the possibility to provide plasticity rules to synapses in hxtorch, which was only possible in PyNN before. E. Müller implemented these changes while this thesis was written.

This highlights that even though it carries complexity and developers need to put effort into becoming familiar with the software if they want to work with lower-level mechanisms, the stack itself is designed very flexibly, allowing even such significant customisations as attempted in this thesis.

¹Idea from E. Müller

Chapter 8

Summary

This bachelor thesis explored the implementation of early-exit on NH. This investigation was lacking in the state of the art, which largely works on standard hardware like GPUs.

The thesis presented the training of a classifier for the Yin-Yang symbol on the partly-analog NH BrainScaleS. It was shown that the hardware allowed the use of multiple strategies to train the model for early-exit, which includes TET loss, regularisation terms working on the measured membrane potential and spikes of the output neurons for each timestep, and custom calculation of neuron activations as decimals based on spikes and potential.

All trained models learned to classify parts of the Yin-Yang symbol after only a fraction of the full runtime originally used for inference. Their accuracy varied, from being worse than the baseline model from the BrainScaleS team to surpassing 90 % accuracy after just five epochs.

One of the trained models was used to also implement early-exit for the inference. Utilising BrainScaleS's Python and C++ interfaces, custom code for the digital and analog components was written to monitor the neurons, determine the confidence of the model and send a stop signal to end the experiment.

Overall, this thesis showed that training for early-exit can be implemented on partly-analog NH. The inference is more challenging, but likely possible if tasks with a longer runtime are chosen to compensate variances in the timing.

BrainScaleS as partly-analog system presented the author with unique challenges in regard to the timing of the code execution as well as the handling of analog observables. On the other hand, its flexible software stack allowed all necessary customisation for early-exit.

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Dr. Müller provided a lot of support during the implementation, explained the software stack, suggested possible implementations and extended the software for BrainScaleS while the thesis was written to add functionality specifically needed for this work.

Use of AI: ChatGPT from OpenAI and Gemini from Google were used during the creation of this thesis. It was used to: search for relevant papers, provide high-level summaries of general concepts and assist with LaTeX, C++ and torch-tensor syntax. All information were checked by the author with the sources cited in text.

AI was not used to generate any part of this work, including text, images or code.

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Ich erkläre, dass ich die Bachelorarbeit selbstständig und ohne unzulässige Inanspruchnahme Dritter verfasst habe.

Ich habe dabei nur die angegebenen Quellen und Hilfsmittel verwendet und die aus diesen wörtlich oder sinngemäß entnommenen Stellen als solche kenntlich gemacht. Die Versicherung selbstständiger Arbeit gilt auch für enthaltene Zeichnungen, Skizzen oder graphische Darstellungen.

Die Bachelorarbeit wurde bisher in gleicher oder ähnlicher Form weder derselben noch einer anderen Prüfungsbehörde vorgelegt und auch nicht veröffentlicht.

Mit der Abgabe der elektronischen Fassung der endgültigen Version der Bachelorarbeit nehme ich zur Kenntnis, dass diese mit Hilfe eines Plagiatserkennungsdienstes auf enthaltene Plagiate geprüft werden kann und ausschließlich für Prüfungszwecke gespeichert wird.

Source Literature

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Acronyms

- AdEx** Neuron model which respects the adaption process, a neuron becomes more or less spiking-happy after it recently spiked. The exponential is used to describe the change in membrane potential. 4, 5, 9, 19, 21, 26
- ANN** Machine learning model which creates an output by processing an input through layers of connected nodes, each node performs calculations based on signals from earlier nodes and the weight of the connections. 1, 2, 6, 9, 11, 12, 16, 21, 26
- CADC** Electronic component of BrainScaleS which converts an analog signal (continuous) into a digital signal (discrete). Applied on all columns of the synapse array in parallel. 19, 23, 24, 34, 44
- CE** A loss function which considers the model's output and the targets as probability distributions and evaluates how different they are to calculate the error. 8, 16, 30, 31, 35, 40, 42, 55, 70
- FPGA** Integrated circuit which can be flexibly reprogrammed.. 11, 19, 46, 49–54, 56
- LI** Neuron model which includes a leak-term which lets the neuron drift back to a resting potential on a lack of input. The neuron does not spike but only accumulates incoming signal. 26, 30
- LIF** Neuron model which includes a leak-term which lets the neuron drift back to a resting potential on a lack of input. 4, 6, 21, 23
- MADC** Electronic component of BrainScaleS which converts an analog signal (continuous) into a digital signal (discrete). Has a much higher sampling rate and resolution than CADCs, but can only sample from two neurons at the same time. 24
- MSE** A loss function using the average of the squared differences from the model's output to the targets to calculate the error. 16, 31, 70
- NH** Hardware which is modelled after the brain's structure. 2, 3, 9–11, 14, 17, 58
- NN** Type of machine learning model inspired by the brain's structure. Structured like a weighted graph. 1, 2, 5, 16
- PPU** Digital processors in BrainScaleS, responsible for plasticity algorithms and neuron control. 19, 20, 26, 27, 45–53, 56, 57

- SAT** Tradeoff between the speed with which a decision is made and the accuracy of the response. 2, 11
- SNN** Machine learning model which creates an output by processing an input through layers of connected nodes, nodes communicate via discrete events (spikes), not continuous signals. 1–19, 23, 25, 26, 28, 29, 45, 47
- TET** Temporal Efficient Training. Proposed by Deng et al., a loss which is calculated for every timestep and combines CE loss with MSE as regularisation. 16, 26, 31, 34, 42, 55, 58
- TIT** Time Inheritance Training. Approach proposed by Deng et al., a model is trained for different runtimes, ranging from short to long, to learn to classify simple examples quickly. 16, 30, 34, 36, 39, 40, 55

Appendix A

Inference With PyNN

The feature to use custom plasticity rules in `hxtorch` did not exist when the implementation of the inference was started. Therefore, it was attempted to implement the inference with PyNN.

The weights determined by the training with `hxtorch` were persisted through Python's `pickle` module. This is how the data could be shared between the notebooks for training and inference.

This chapter briefly describes how the necessary translation from the model trained with `hxtorch` to PyNN was done and presents the result of the inference.

A.1 Translation To PyNN

The structure of the network could be replicated quite simply using PyNN's `Population` and `Projection`. One challenge was that PyNN differentiates between excitatory synapses with positive weights and inhibitory synapses with negative weights. Each synapse in `hxtorch` resulted in two synapses in PyNN.

Listing 1 shows how the `Populations` are created and how the weights are used to build the `Projections` between them. The function `hxtorch_weights_to_connector` creates a `FromListConnector`, which defines the weights for the synapses in the `Projection` in the form (presynaptic index, postsynaptic index, weight) [79]. In `hxtorch`, this addressing of specific neuron-pairs happens through the inherent format for the weights, a tensor where each cell belongs to one pair. The initial weights of 0 for the `StaticSynapse` are replaced by the loaded weights.

The `connection_type` is used to filter for positive or negative weights and the `post_syn_indices` are used to select a subset of the postsynaptic neurons. This was used to restrict the output neurons to one instead of three, as otherwise the placement of the network on the chip failed.

```
1 hidden_pop = pynn.Population(HIDDEN_SIZE, pynn.cells.HXNeuron(  
2     **neuron_params  
3 ))
```

```

4 output_pop = pynn.Population(OUTPUT_SIZE, pynn.cells.HXNeuron(
5     plasticity_rule=plasticity_rule,
6     **neuron_params
7 ))
8
9 # load the weights from the training
10 linear_o_weight_bak = pickle.load( # format: [ 3, 120 ]
11     open(f'./data/linear_o_weight_tit_2.pkl', 'rb')).data
12 linear_o_weight_bak *= weight_scale # apply scale used during training
13
14 # create connections
15 hidden_output_projection_inh = pynn.Projection(
16     hidden_pop, output_pop,
17     hxtorch_weights_to_connector(linear_o_weight_bak,
18     connection_type="inhibitory", post_syn_indices=[1]), # 1=yang
19     synapse_type=pynn.standardmodels.synapses.StaticSynapse(weight=0),
20     receptor_type="inhibitory"
21 )
22
23 hidden_output_projection_exi = pynn.Projection(
24     hidden_pop, output_pop,
25     hxtorch_weights_to_connector(linear_o_weight_bak,
26     connection_type="excitatory", post_syn_indices=[1]), # 1=yang
27     synapse_type=pynn.standardmodels.synapses.StaticSynapse(weight=0),
28     receptor_type="excitatory"
29 )

```

Listing 1: Creation of Populations and Projections for inference with PyNN

The connection between the input and hidden layer was done similarly, however with some added complexity. The input spikes needed to be translated to PyNN. For that, five input Projections were defined, each one with a SpikeSourceArray that contained the spike time of one of the four input coordinates or the bias. Listing 2 shows the creation of these Populations. The network therefore needed ten Projections between input and hidden layer, two for each of the five input Populations.

```

1 input_coordinates = [0.5, 0.1]
2 input_coordinates = [ input_coordinates[0], input_coordinates[1],
3     1 - input_coordinates[0], 1 - input_coordinates[1] ]
4
5 input_spike_times = coordinates_to_spiketimes(input_coordinates)
6
7 for i in range(INPUTS):
8     input_pop = pynn.Population(INPUT_REPITITIONS, pynn.cells.
9     SpikeSourceArray(
10         spike_times=input_spike_times[i]
11     ))
12     input_pops.append(input_pop)

```

Listing 2: Creation of Input Populations

While being quite complex, the translation of the network structure was possible. The neuron parameters for threshold, rest and leak potential were selected like in hxtorch.

A.2 Inference Result

The plot in Fig. 20 shows the membrane potential trace for the output neuron responsible for the Yin (blue) and Yang (red) classes. Because of the restriction to a single output neuron, they were collected in two separate runs. The input point was $x=0.75, y=0.1$, located at the bottom right of the Yin-Yang symbol, clearly inside the Yin class. The dots in the figure show the input spike times, which could be successfully replicated with the input populations. As comparison, Fig. 21 shows the activations for the output neurons of the model in hxtorch for the same point, timestep 30 equals 0.06 ms.

Figure 20: Membrane potential for output neuron for the Yin (blue) and Yang (red) class when provided with input spikes for $x=0.75, y=0.1$.

The difference between the outputs from PyNN and hxtorch is clearly visible. The difference between the Yin classes and the other classes is significant in hxtorch, but barely existing in PyNN. Additionally, the output neurons in PyNN spike way more than in hxtorch.

This behaviour clearly shows that the translation was not successful. A bug in the weight translation could be possible, but unittests were written to reduce the likelihood of this. A possible cause for this behaviour are differences in the neuron behaviour because the used parameters are interpreted differently by PyNN and hxtorch.

Detailed debugging of the root cause was not attempted, because the functionality to provide plasticity rules to hxtorch was available soon after this. The focus was therefore shifted to hxtorch, where the possible scaling issues observed here could be avoided.

Figure 21: Membrane potential for output neuron for the Yin class when provided with input spikes for $x=0.75, y=0.1$.